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Executive Summary

TUSAIL (Training in Upscaling Particle Systems: Advancing Industry across Length-scale) aims to establish reliable upscaling methodologies and tools that utilize physics-based modeling to predict the behavior of large industrial unit operations and processes. The project focuses on developing three complementary upscaling approaches: (i) population balance modeling (PBM), (ii) coarse-grained meso-particle methods, and (iii) coupling between discrete and continuum methods.

In the first report of the WP3, a comprehensive state of the art literature review on the discrete and continuum modelling approaches for particle ensembles and particulate flows was presented. The report's emphasis was on the novel methods for offline and online coupling of discrete and continuum modelling as well as on methods for efficient time-extrapolation of particle simulations.

The second progress report presented first application examples and preliminary results from the ESRs who are contributing to WP3. From a thematic perspective individual contributions covered micropolar theory, material point method (MPM), coupling of discrete and continuum models in purely solids and gas-solids systems and time-extrapolation.

The current report presents further progressed results of the involved ESRs. Moreover, each Section includes a thorough discussion on how those results were obtained. What lessons were learnt and what finally resulted in success? In summary, these individual lists of dos and don'ts compile to best practice guidelines for the coupling between discrete and continuum methods.

Preface

In this report from TUSAIL’s third work-package on **Discrete to Continuum Models** we aim to present **Best Practice Guidelines** for pursuing research in this field.

To achieve this objective, we asked our sub-cohort of five Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) to first concisely present their current state of research – reflecting two years of PhD work. This first task can be regarded as a natural succession of our preceding report on **Application Examples**, which collected first preliminary results. However, for this report we advised our ESRs to put emphasis on an honest reflection on the way these results have been achieved. With this second task our ESRs were asked to distill their experiences as young researchers into individual best practice research guidelines.

Consequently, each individual section of this report has a concluding subsection on **Reflection on Best Practice Research**, which discussed scope and limitations of the individual research efforts (in terms of validity and applicability) and honestly reports on successes and pitfalls during their research journey. Reflecting on these experiences finally leads to identification of general “dos and don’ts” for developing discrete to continuum models.

This report has been written by our ESRs themselves and thus reflects their development towards becoming independent researchers. As work-package leaders, we interacted solely by providing advice towards the common structure of this report. More specifically, we tried to convince our ESRs to keep the presentation of results concise and pertinent with focus on distilling best practices instead. Reading this report, you will see that we somewhat didn’t succeed with this specific requests. In this phase of their PhD work, our ESRs are in the progress of writing their journal papers, which is reflected by their sometimes very comprehensive result sections. Keeping in mind the ESRs’ overall work load, we however didn’t insist in shortening these sections, because in the end their interpretations of best practice research can be readily found at the end of each sub-section.

With this introductory words, we wish you a pleasant read!

Stefan Pirker (JKU) and Alex Munnoch (JM) WP3 work-package leaders

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Chapter 1

Discrete to continuum upscaling for rotational kinematics

1.1 Introduction

Granular soils are made of discrete particles that interact with each other through frictional contacts. Any change of properties at grain level, the microscale, affects the response of the material on the macro-scale. It has been shown that the particle shape is one factor that influences the rotational behaviour of the material [1], [2].

Through discrete-to-continuum (D2C) upscaling methods, the discrete particle data such as particle mass, particle velocity and contact force can be mapped on continuous fields like density, velocity, and stress. Following the approach by Goldhirsch [3] and Weinhart [4], [5], and using a smoothening function, we develop a D2C method to transform particle properties related to rotation like discrete angular velocity, angular momentum, tangential forces, and contact torque to non-classical micropolar fields like continuum angular velocity, curvature, skew-symmetric stress, and couple stress.

This section will introduce best practices on how to develop new D2C transformations with a focus on rotational kinematics, namely macro-rotation, micro-rotation and curvature. Before doing so, a brief introduction to the theoretical background and the general ideas behind the D2C method by Goldhirsch and Weinhart is given. Details are given in the previous reports. Different possibilities for upscaling those kinematics are motivated and discussed based on simple test cases where an estimate of the outcome can be made. With this understanding, they will be applied on a Cartesian shear cell to pick one favoured definition and to understand rotational behaviour in the shear cell. Along the line, best practices for using this D2C method will be introduced.

1.2 Micropolar theory for granular materials

As introduced by the Cosserat brothers, micropolar continua have two separate rotations on two different scales [6], [7]. Micromechanical considerations help identifying those two different rotations. In difference to classic continua, a material point in a micropolar continua has not only translational degrees of freedom, but also rotational. Therefore, a velocity and an angular velocity can be assigned to every material point. Through this the kinematic fields of macro-rotation, micro-rotation and curvature arise [8].

The macro-rotation is the corresponding rotation tensor to the rate of deformation which corresponds to the average particle velocity. The deformation due to the average particle rotation is the micro-rotation, and the gradient of the particle rotation is curvature. The difference between macro- and micro-rotation is the relative rotation [8].

Those definitions are not only valid for granular materials, but for micropolar continua in general. Instead of using deformation, the sum of the velocity gradient and the micro-rotation is often referred to as Cosserat deformation [9]. Please refer to previous reports for details on this topic.

1.3 Discrete to continuum upscaling

This section introduces the discrete to continuum (D2C) upscaling method which got introduced by [3] and was further developed by [4], [10], [11]. We will first introduce the general idea and functionality of it before discussing several possibilities for a D2C upscaling of rotational kinematic fields which we introduced in Sec. 1.2. This can be used as best practice guideline for the introduction of new D2C methods.

1.3.1 General idea¹

The idea behind coarse graining can be explained the easiest at the mass density. On microscopic scale, the mass density ρ_m on a point \mathbf{r} at time t is defined using statistical mechanics as

$$\rho_m(\mathbf{r}, t) \equiv \sum_i m_i \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i(t)), \quad (1.1)$$

where $\delta(\mathbf{r})$ denotes the Dirac delta function. This is only a singular entity. In coarse graining, this Dirac function is replaced by a smoothing coarse graining function ϕ [3]:

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_i m_i \phi(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i(t)). \quad (1.2)$$

¹This subsection has been adapted from the preceding report on *Work Package 3: Application examples and results of continuum theory upscaling*.

The coarse graining function can have several shapes, but usually a Gaussian function or Lucy polynomial with a cutoff is used. Anyway, the exact definition of the smoothing function is often not as influential as the chosen length scale w , and to be more precise its relation to the particle diameter, $\frac{w}{d}$. Whereas small length scale give a representation on microlevel/particle scale, large length scales smoothen the fields too much. Therefore, it is necessary to chose a length scale in between, normally between $0.7 \leq \frac{w}{d} \leq 1.5$ to achieve a representation on macroscale [5]. However, small gradients are necessary to allow such large REVs [3].

Having a definition of the density field, it is easy to derive a coarse grained momentum and a coarse grained velocity field. The time derivative of the momentum leads to a coarse grained expression of the stress tensor. For details on classic fields, consult [3], [10]–[12].

1.3.2 Rotational kinematic fields

As introduced in Sec. 1.2, a macro- and a micro-rotation occur in micropolar continua and the difference between them, the relative rotation, contributes to the mechanical work done in a system. From a D2C point of view, Goldhirsch [3] has motivated those two rotations via the local angular momentum density, \mathbf{L} ,

$$\mathbf{L} \equiv \sum_i (m_i(\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}) \times \mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{L}_i) \phi(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i). \quad (1.3)$$

The first term is an angular momentum due to the lever between a translating particle and a D2C center (see Fig. 1.1). We can relate this angular momentum to a macroscopic rotation and hence the vorticity which is a classic continuum field. The second term \mathbf{L}_i is the angular momentum of a particle around itself and hence related to micro-rotation. We will use those angular momenta to find possible definitions for macro- and micro-rotation. Those, and curvature, will be discussed in the following subsection based on simple test cases. We define the following steps to introduce new D2C transitions:

1. Motivate new field
2. Formulate test cases with expected outcome and test if the new D2C transition can meet the expectation
3. Examine if the new D2C transition can handle areas close to a boundary correctly
4. Examine the influence of the D2C width
5. Application

FIGURE 1.1: Two different possible rotation

1.3.2.1 Macro-rotation

Based on the macroscopic angular momentum, we define a macro-rotation which we call \mathbf{w}^{CG} . To do so, we upscale the angular momentum due to the lever between the particle velocity and D2C center. To obtain a rotation, we need to multiply the angular momentum with the inverse of the moment of inertia. The question here is how to define the moment of inertia. Since we are taking the angular momentum with respect to the D2C center, simple upscaling of the particles moment of inertia does not make sense. Hence, we upscale the moment of inertia with respect to the D2C center using the parallel axis theorem. The moment of inertia of a particle with respect to the D2C center is then given as

$$\mathbf{J}_i = \mathbf{I}_i + m_i[(\mathbf{R}_i \cdot \mathbf{R}_i)\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{R}_i \otimes \mathbf{R}_i], \quad (1.4)$$

with $\mathbf{R}_i = \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i$ (see Fig. 1.1 for a visual explanation). Another way to obtain macro-rotation is via the skew-symmetric part of the velocity gradient which is the classic velocity. The two definitions read:

$$\mathbf{w}^{\text{CG}} = \left(\sum_i \mathbf{J}_i \phi \right)^{-1} \cdot \left(\sum_i m_i (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}) \times \mathbf{v}_i \phi \right), \quad \mathbf{w}^{\text{vort}} = \text{skw}(\nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}) \quad (1.5)$$

where \mathbf{V} is the coarse grained velocity field obtained from the momentum density [3]:

$$\mathbf{V}(\mathbf{r}, t) \equiv \frac{\sum_i m_i \mathbf{v}_i \phi(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i)}{\sum_i m_i \phi(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_i)}. \quad (1.6)$$

We will discuss those two different definitions on three different test cases of a line of 64 monodisperse particles with a diameter $d = 0.98$ and a distance between their center of masses of 1. Hence, the particles are just not in contact but close enough to consider them as dense. In addition, we do not have to think about static fields and can focus on the kinematics. In each test case, we prescribe a different velocity to the particles:

1. constant, $v_{i,y} = 1$,

2. alternating, $v_{i,y} = \pm 1$,
3. constant gradient, $v_{i,y} = \frac{i}{N_p}$ with i being the i -th particle in the line and N_p the total number of particles.

Fig. 1.2 shows the different macro-rotations for those test cases with different upscaling widths w . The homogeneous distribution of the particles along a long makes it easy to interpret the results. The expected vorticity for constant particle velocity is zero because the line of particles purely translates without any rotation (Fig. 1.2, top row). \mathbf{w}^{CG} cannot reproduce that across upscaling widths. We can observe one positive and one negative peak per particle. Every time a D2C point is equidistant to the two next neighbouring particles, \mathbf{w}^{CG} returns zero because their angular momenta cancel. This is the case if the D2C point is in the middle between two particles or at the center of a particle. Hence, we get two peaks per particle. The classic definition, \mathbf{w}^{vort} , successfully returns zero across upscaling widths.

Consequently, only half as many oscillations can be observed in the alternating case (Fig. 1.2 second row) for \mathbf{w}^{CG} . The classic vorticity definition, \mathbf{w}^{vort} , returns strong amplitudes on microscopic level due to the steep gradients on particle level. Those get reasonably smoothed out with increasing upscaling width.

The third case of a constant gradient is shown in row three and four. \mathbf{w}^{CG} increases with increasing particle velocity even though the gradient remains the same which is not what we expect from that case. The reason for that is that the D2C window is too small for an upscaling width of $\frac{w}{d} = 0.2$ to take more than one particle into account. Hence, we can see a big amplitude which in fact does not exist on macro level. The classic definition on the other hand perfectly returns half of the applied gradient.

To summarise, \mathbf{w}^{CG} has problems in returning accurate results for small coarse graining widths, and \mathbf{w}^{vort} matches the expectations well. Both definitions have problems towards boundaries and the data close to a boundary cannot be relied. Those dependences are not for all boundaries given the definitions of the fields. Due to the nature of the cross product and the gradient, only one out of three directions will be influenced. In a conservative estimation, the full support of $3w$ should be neglected, but due to the shape of the Gaussian function, a smaller area can be considered unreliable.

In Fig. 1.3, we show the dependence of the two definitions on the upscaling width w based on the mean value in a range of $\frac{x}{d} \in [15, 49]$. We do not consider the full chain of particles to avoid the influence of the two boundaries. It can be seen that \mathbf{w}^{vort} is fairly independent from the upscaling width for all cases. \mathbf{w}^{CG} on the other hand is only converging towards a plateau for $\frac{w}{d} > 0.5$ for the first two cases and even $\frac{w}{d} > 1.5$ for the last case. We can therefore conclude that \mathbf{w}^{CG} is overall influenced by the microscopic behaviour of the particles, whereas \mathbf{w}^{vort} is a true macroscopic field.

FIGURE 1.2: Three test cases for macro-rotation with three different coarse graining widths. Rows are different cases, columns different definitions of macro-rotation.

FIGURE 1.3: Dependence of the macro-rotation on the coarse graining width for three different test cases in an area far away from the boundary, $x \in [15, 49]$. Rows are different test cases, columns different definitions of macro-rotation.

1.3.2.2 Micro-rotation

The second term of Eq. (1.3) refers to the angular momentum of a particle around its own center of mass. To obtain a rotation, ω^{CM} , we need to multiply it with the inverse of the coarse grained particle moment of inertia. We define a second micro-rotation, ω^{PAT} , based on the same concept of using the angular momentum and the inverse of moment of inertia, but we move the reference point from the particle center of mass to the D2C center using the parallel axes theorem as done

in Eq. (1.4). This way, we can define a field based on material points and hence a continuum field. Lastly, we define a simple version, ω^P , which directly coarse grains the particle angular velocity to compare if the more complicated way via angular momenta is actually necessary. The three definitions read:

$$\omega^{\text{CM}} \equiv \left(\sum_i \mathbf{I}_i \phi \right)^{-1} \cdot \left(\sum_i \mathbf{I}_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \phi \right), \quad \omega^{\text{PAT}} \equiv \left(\sum_i \mathbf{J}_i \phi \right)^{-1} \cdot \left(\sum_i \mathbf{J}_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \phi \right), \quad (1.7)$$

$$\omega^P \equiv \frac{\sum_i \boldsymbol{\omega}_i \phi}{\sum_i \phi}.$$

We will discuss those three different definitions on three different test cases of a chain of 64 mono disperse particles with a diameter $d = 0.98$ and a distance between their center of masses of 1. Hence, the particles are just not in contact but close enough to consider them as dense. In addition, we do not have to think about static fields and can focus on the kinematics. In each test case, we prescribe a different angular velocity to the particles:

1. constant, $\omega_{i,y} = 1$,
2. alternating, $\omega_{i,y} = \pm 1$,
3. constant gradient, $\omega_{i,y} = \frac{i}{N_p}$ with i being the i -th particle in the chain and N_p the number of particles.

Fig. 1.4 shows the different micro-rotations for those test cases with different upscaling widths w . The homogeneous distribution of the particles along a chain makes it easy to interpret the results. The expected micro-rotation for a constant particle angular velocity is the prescribed particle angular velocity (Fig. 1.4, first row) which can be reproduced by all three definitions across all upscaling widths. Hence, they pass the sanity check.

An alternating sense of rotation should smooth out the rotations. Small upscaling widths return oscillations with large amplitude and a wave length of two particles due to the fact that discrete data gets reproduced (see Fig. 1.4, second row). Still, for a macroscopic width of $\frac{w}{d} = 1$, oscillations are visible. At this width a maximum of 7 particles is taken into account for a Gaussian kernel when the D2C center coincides with a particle center of mass. Only if the D2C center coincides with the midpoint between two particle center of mass, the result is zero because there is an equal amount of particles on both sides and their angular velocities are cancelling. Whereas ω^P and ω^{CM} are returning the exact same result, ω^{PAT} gives larger amplitudes.

All three definitions are successfully reproducing an alternating gradient in rotation (last row), and do not seem to be influenced by the width w .

To summarise, all three definitions return similar results in all cases and can successfully upscale constant and alternating angular velocities as well as angular velocities with a gradient. Hereby,

ω^P and ω^{CM} actually return the exact same results. Similar to the macro-rotation, all definitions have problems reproducing reliable data close to a boundary. Hereby, ω^{PAT} is more dependent on it than the two other definitions. This can be explained with the dependence of \mathbf{J} on w . The larger a coarse graining cell is chosen, the larger the moment of inertia gets, as it can be seen in Eq. (1.4). It is of interest if there are conditions under which those three definitions would differ more. Since the main difference is the definition of the moment of inertia, particle shape might be the way to go. However, this is beyond the scope of this report.

FIGURE 1.4: Three test cases for micro-rotation with three different coarse graining widths. Rows are the different cases, columns different definitions of micro-rotation.

When studying the dependence of those three micro-rotations on the upscaling width, slight differences between ω^P and ω^{CM} compared to ω^{PAT} can be seen. While they are all capable of correctly upscaling a constant value (see first row Fig. 1.5), they do differ slightly for the two other cases. As soon as the upscaling width is large enough to leave the discrete area ($\frac{w}{d} \approx 0.5$), ω^P and ω^{CM} return a constant value of zero. ω^{PAT} on the other hand has more difficulties in that regard. Even though the deviations are extremely small, it cannot successfully return zero which can be explained again by the dependence of \mathbf{J} on the upscaling width. Similarly, we observe a higher dependence on the upscaling width for ω^{PAT} in the third case.

1.3.2.3 Curvature

As discussed in Sec. 1.2, the curvature is the gradient of the micro-rotation. Hence, it can be obtained by post processing previously upscaled fields:

$$\kappa^{CM} \equiv \nabla \otimes \omega^{CM}, \quad \kappa^{PAT} \equiv \nabla \otimes \omega^{PAT}, \quad \kappa^P \equiv \nabla \otimes \omega^P. \quad (1.8)$$

FIGURE 1.5: Dependence of the micro-rotation on the coarse graining width for three different test cases in an area far away from the boundary, $x \in [15, 285]$. Rows are different test cases, columns different definitions of micro-rotation.

When discussing the same test cases as in Sec. 1.3.2.2, only the xy component of curvature is relevant because we have a gradient in x direction and a rotation around y . In all three test, we can observe the same features for the three different definitions since those are inherited from the respective definition of micro-rotation. Reasonably, the curvature is zero for constant angular velocity (see Fig. 1.6), and returns oscillations for oscillations in the micro-rotation. We see the same differences for the second and third test case and with the same weaknesses close to the boundaries.

FIGURE 1.6: Three test cases for curvature with three different coarse graining widths. Rows are the different test cases, columns the different definitions of curvature.

1.4 Application results ²

Shearing of granular materials is a widely studied problem [13]–[15] and in particular interesting due to the existence of a shear band where particles rotate relatively a lot [6], [16]. This simulation of a three-dimensional Cartesian split-bottom shear cell was originally carried out by Roy *et al.* [15] on sheared wet granular media using the DEM simulation software MercuryDPM [17]. However, in this study, only dry granular media is considered. We study how the kinematic fields introduced in Sec. 1.3.2 behave under complex conditions and decide on one definition to study the influence of rolling friction. As shown in the preceding report on *Work Package 3: Application examples and results of continuum theory upscaling*, rolling friction is the most influential on micropolar effects out of all contact frictions.

All parameters of the simulation are dimensionless. The bulk consists of 19.793 monodisperse particles with a particle diameter of $d = 1$. The walls are created out of the same particles to avoid slip. The two halves of the shear cell are then moving in opposite directions with a shear velocity of $\dot{\gamma} = 0.0125$ inducing a shear on the bulk. Due to the low shear velocity, the simulation reaches a steady state immediately where the kinetic energy is constant which is ideal for a D2C transition. The data is averaged over time to eliminate noise due to avoid the influence of noise and upscaled using the previously introduced D2C methods. Spatial averaging is not applied and the data is derived from the half-depth of the shear cell. Small deviations can be observed throughout the depth of the shear cell, but the general behaviour is the same due to the cell's periodicity.

Contacts between particles are simulated as spring-dashpot system [18]–[20]. The sliding friction is set to $\mu_s = 0.5$ for all simulations. The rolling friction is modelled as elastic-plastic spring-dashpot as well [20] is set to zero, except for Sec. 1.4.4 where the following cases were used: $\mu_r = \{0, 0.5, 1\}$.

1.4.1 Macro-rotation

The test cases have shown that the macro-rotations are oscillating for small upscaling widths which are getting smoother with increasing upscaling width w . The same can be seen in the Cartesian shear cell. Fig. 1.7 shows the macro-rotation inside the shear band along the height of the shear cell for different upscaling widths w . Both definitions show very similar behaviour, only the amplitudes on microscale differ. This difference does not matter at this point because the interest in macro-rotations lays on macroscopic upscaling widths. The highest macro-rotation can be observed of the bottom at the shear cell which is due to the induced shear at the split

²The introductory part of this section has been adapted from the preceding report on *Work Package 3: Application examples and results of continuum theory upscaling*.

bottom. Unlike the micro-rotation, the macro-rotation is not influenced at this wall due to the nature of their definitions as cross product and gradients, respectively.

FIGURE 1.7: Macro-rotation for different w inside the shear band along the height of the Cartesian shear cell: ω^{CG} left, ω^{vort} right.

When looking at the mean of the values in the range of $\frac{z}{d} = [8, 12]$, the influence of the upscaling width, without a strong influence of the boundaries, can be observed (see Fig. 1.8). Again, both definitions show a very similar behaviour with differences in the microscale which can be explained by the small upscaling width. The smaller w is chosen, the more discrete the obtained fields get which means that they are highly dependent on the presence of particles in a small D2C window. Whereas ω^{vort} is only dependent on particle velocity, ω^{CG} additionally depends on the distance between a particle and the D2C center which can explain the different behaviours. Hence, those curves might look very different on the microscopic scale when the observed area is slightly moved.

Since both definitions are very similar and do not show significant differences, ω^{vort} is chosen for the friction study because it is easier to obtain and more reliable when looking at the test cases.

FIGURE 1.8: Dependence of the mean of macro-rotation inside the shear band along the height of the Cartesian shear cell in the range $\frac{z}{d} = [8, 12]$: ω^{CG} left, ω^{vort} right.

1.4.2 Micro-rotation

The test cases for the micro-rotation in Sec. 1.3.2.2 have shown the same results for ω^P and ω^{CM} . Hence it is interesting to observe if they are exactly the same under complex conditions as a shear cell. Only a slight difference for ω^{PAT} was observed in the test cases due to the dependence of the moved moment of inertia on the upscaling width w .

Fig. 1.9 shows the three different micro-rotations inside the shear band along the height of the shear cell for different upscaling widths w (top row) and a direct comparison of the definitions for different w (bottom row). Again, strong and similar oscillations with an average wave length of about one particle diameter are observed on microscale which get smoother with increasing w . The peaks for $\frac{w}{d} = 0.2$ are at the same locations which means that all definitions capture the particle positions consistently. Overall, the differences are minor. The highest micro-rotations can be observed towards the bottom of the shear cell which are due to the split bottom which is inducing the shear.

FIGURE 1.9: Micro-rotation for different w inside the shear band along the height of the Cartesian shear cell. Top row: ω^{CM} left, ω^{PAT} middle, ω^P right. Bottom row: comparison of the three definitions at different upscaling widths.

When looking at the mean of the values in the range of $\frac{z}{d} = [8, 12]$, the influence of the upscaling width, without a strong influence of the boundaries, can be observed (see Fig. 1.10). Again, all definitions show a very similar behaviour, and as seen in the test cases, only ω^{PAT} differs slightly due to the influence of w on the moved moment of inertia. It can also be seen that the oscillations for $\frac{w}{d} = 0.2$ are having a similar mean value as the micro-rotations for larger w .

Since all three definitions are very similar and do not show significant differences, ω^P is chosen for the friction study because it is the simplest definitions and easiest to obtain from discrete data.

FIGURE 1.10: Dependence of the mean of micro-rotation inside the shear band along the height of the Cartesian shear cell in the range $\frac{z}{d} = [8, 12]$: ω^{CM} left, ω^{PAT} middle, ω^P right.

1.4.3 Curvature

The test cases for the curvature in Sec. 1.3.2.3 have shown very similar results for all definitions with slight differences between κ^{PAT} and the two other, κ^{CM} and κ^P . Unlike for macro- and micro-rotation, the data of curvature is not observed along the center line because it is showing a vertex at zero. Instead, the curvature is analysed along a line 1.5 particle diameters to the left side of the center line, an area where the maximum values can be found.

Fig. 1.11 shows the three different curvatures inside the shear band along the height of the shear cell for different upscaling widths w (top row) and a direct comparison of the definitions for different w (bottom row). Again, strong and similar oscillations with an average wave length of about one particle diameter are observed on microscale which get smoother with increasing w . However, the peaks of the oscillations are several orders of magnitude larger than the smoothed fields which means that neighbouring particles do have strongly different rotations in an overall homogenous field of rotation. The peaks for $\frac{w}{d} = 0.2$ are at the same locations which means that all definitions capture the particle positions consistently. Overall, the differences are minor. Unlike micro- and macro-rotation, the highest curvature is not close to the bottom but more or less consistent throughout the whole shear band.

When looking at the mean of the values in the range of $\frac{z}{d} = [8, 12]$, the influence of the upscaling width, without a strong influence of the boundaries, can be observed (see Fig. 1.12). Again, all definitions show a very similar behaviour, and as seen in the test cases, only κ^{PAT} differs slightly in the are of $\frac{w}{d} = [0.5, 1]$ due to the influence of w on ω^{PAT} . In all cases a value close to zero is reached above $\frac{w}{d} = 0.5$ which means that the curvature in the system is consistently small.

FIGURE 1.11: Curvature for different w inside the shear band along the height of the Cartesian shear cell. Top row: κ^{CM} left, κ^{PAT} middle, κ^{P} right. Bottom row: comparison of the three definitions at different upscaling widths.

Since all definitions are very similar and do not show significant differences, κ^{P} is chosen for the friction study because it is consistent with the choice of ω^{P} .

FIGURE 1.12: Dependence of the mean of curvature inside the shear band along the height of the Cartesian shear cell in the range $\frac{z}{d} = [8, 12]$: κ^{CM} left, κ^{PAT} middle, κ^{P} right.

1.4.4 Influence of rolling friction

As shown in the preceding report on *Work Package 3: Application examples and results of continuum theory upscaling*, rolling friction is the most influential contact friction with regard to micropolar behaviour. Hence, it is interesting to see how rolling friction influences the two micropolar kinematic quantities of relative rotation and curvature.

Fig. 1.13 shows the influence of rolling friction on relative rotation and curvature along the height (top row) and along the width of the shear cell (bottom row). Since the curvature is zero in the center of the shear cell, it is plotted 1.5 particle diameters to the left of the center line.

As before, there does not seem to be a noticeable difference along most of the height for relative rotation and curvature. Only towards the bottom at $\frac{z}{d} \leq 4$, the rolling friction promotes relative rotation and hence micropolarity. However, the difference between $\mu_r = 0.5$ and $\mu_r = 1$ is rather small which indicates that there is a certain threshold. The opposite effect can be observed for curvature where the effect is going down with increasing rolling friction. Again, it is important to be careful with data close to the wall as discussed previously.

But also when observing the rotational kinematics along the width (see Fig. 1.13, bottom row), the influence of rolling friction is clearly visible. Whereas they almost fully cancel each other without rolling friction, the micro-rotation is getting smaller with increasing μ_r . As expected, higher friction is leading to less rotation of individual particles but the rotation on continuum scale, the macro-rotation, is less influenced by that. The arising relative rotation is work-conjugate to skew-symmetric stress. Due to the different reactions to rolling friction, it would be interesting to examine the couple stress which is beyond the scope of this report. However, it is important to note that this D2C transition is not reliable in the presence of steep gradients and hence, the curvature along the width has to be treated with care.

FIGURE 1.13: Relative rotation and curvature for different rolling frictions μ_r inside the Cartesian shear cell. Top row: Along the height with $w^{\text{vort}} - \omega^{\text{p}}$ left, and κ^{p} right. Bottom row: Along the width at $\frac{z}{d} = 2$ with $w^{\text{vort}} - \omega^{\text{p}}$ left, and κ^{p} right.

1.5 Best Practice Guidelines

In this chapter we have demonstrated several best practices on several levels. This section will be used to reflect on those. Three different best practice levels can be identified: introducing new fields in a D2C transition in general, upscaling rotational kinematics, and upscaling in general.

Introducing new fields in a D2C method can be challenging in many ways. First of all, it is important to have a fundamental understanding of the aspired continuum field in general, and to use this knowledge to find a relation between the discrete particle world and the continuum level. This does not necessarily lead to one distinct D2C transition but may give rise to several options as shown in the previous sections. In any case it is important to understand the behaviour of newly introduced D2C transitions, but even more so if more than one option is available. In order to do so, simple controlled test cases should be formulated where an expected outcome can be defined. At the same time it is important to examine the behavior across upscaling widths to understand how they work for particle and continuum scale. Furthermore the behaviour close to a boundary needs to be examined because many D2C fields are not accurate in those regions and require a correction close there. However, finding a correction is not trivial in most cases which is why ignoring data close to a boundary should always be considered in the first place. In general, not many corrections are known to the author, except for the stress field [10]. Having understood the different definitions, they can be applied to a real case to finally choose on one. Defining distinct criteria helps choosing one, but most important, one should not be afraid of picking the simplest version. It might not be the most sophisticated version, but the easiest to work with without loss of information. In any case, it is always important to remember that the result might be dependent on the examined situation and the outcome might be different for another regime or material.

As best practices for upscaling rotational kinematics we have shown in this report that using a small upscaling width is not necessarily useful because rotations can fluctuate a lot between particles, even more than velocity does in a particle flow. However, it can be useful to get a better understanding of the granular system itself even though that might not be used in a publication. Furthermore, doing the same procedure for non-spherical particles might lead to larger differences between ω^{PAT} and the other definitions. In that case, examining those and their meaning would be interesting, but are unfortunately beyond the scope of this report.

Last but not least, general best practices for D2C transitions are time averaging of data in a steady state to avoid noise from discrete particle and to observe long-lasting continuous behaviour. For that, it is also important to find a plateau in the upscaling width analysis to ensure independence from the upscaling width. Further best practices on general upscaling can be found in [4], [5], [11].

To summarise, continuous fields can be achieved from discrete data using D2C transitions to e.g. formulate constitutive laws. As shown several aspects need to be considered like the influence of the upscaling width or behaviour close to boundaries. However, lot of insights in to the granular system can be gained on several scales. Nevertheless it is always crucial to have a solid physical understanding of discrete and continuous quantities when new transitions are implemented.

1.6 References

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Chapter 2

Multi-regime continuum modelling for granular materials

2.1 Modified Cam-Clay

The modified Cam-Clay (MCC) model, a smooth approximation of the original Cam-Clay, is a geotechnical constitutive relation applicable to both under consolidated and over consolidated soils. The yield surface is represented by an ellipse in the $q - p$ plane, with the length corresponding to the preconsolidation ratio p_c , Figure 2.1. The model predicts the critical state if the stress path is on the intersection point of the yield surface and the critical state line ($\frac{1}{2}p_c$), plastic dilation on the left side of the intersection, while plastic compaction on the right side.

FIGURE 2.1: modified Cam-Clay yield surface

The yield surface takes the form

$$\Phi^{MCC}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, a) = [a(p_c) - p(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) - p_t]^2 + \left(\frac{q(\boldsymbol{\sigma})}{M}\right)^2 - a(p_c)^2, \quad (2.1)$$

where M is the slope of the critical state line, p_t is the tensile pressure, $a = \frac{1}{2}(p_c + p_t)$ is a hardening parameter related to the consolidation pressure p_c . The stress invariants, hydrostatic pressure and deviatoric stress (von-Mises effective stress) are

$$p = -\frac{1}{3}\text{trace}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) \quad q = \sqrt{3J_2(\mathbf{s})} = \sqrt{(3/2)\mathbf{s} : \mathbf{s}} \quad (2.2)$$

with J_2 , the second invariant of the stress tensor, in terms of the deviatoric stress tensor $\mathbf{s} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} + p\mathbf{I}$. The associative plastic flow rule of the modified Cam-Clay is

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^p = \dot{\gamma} \left[\frac{3}{M^2} \mathbf{s} + 2(a - p - p_t) \mathbf{I} \right] \quad (2.3)$$

The hardening rule defines the shape of the yield surface by adjusting the preconsolidation pressure p_c in response to the incremental change in the plastic volumetric strain $\Delta\varepsilon_v^p$. This relationship is expressed

$$p_c = p_{c0} e^{-\frac{v_0}{\lambda - \kappa} \Delta\varepsilon_v^p} \quad (2.4)$$

where p_{c0} is the initial overconsolidation pressure defined as the maximum amount of mean effective stress that a material has undergone.

Isotropic linear elasticity may be sufficient for situations when the pressures ranges are small [1]. On the other hand, a non-linear elasticity may be necessary for large pressure ranges. The classical form of modified Cam Clay includes non-linear isotropic elasticity with the evolution equation for the hydrostatic pressure governed by the increment of elastic volumetric strain

$$p = p_0 e^{-\frac{v_0}{\kappa} \Delta\varepsilon_v^e} \quad (2.5)$$

2.1.1 Capped Drucker-Prager

The capped Drucker-Prager bounds the modified Cam-Clay elliptical yield surface with a cap. This serves to modify the shape of the yield surface, and enables the model to capture plastic compaction during (possibly pure) hydrostatic compression. The implemented model is a multi-surface model, defining the modified cam clay yield surface and Drucker-Prager yield surface. The intersection of these two which is treated by sub-differential surfaces as described by [1].

FIGURE 2.2: capped Drucker-Prager yield surface

The Drucker-Prager cone is described by the yield surface

$$\Phi^{DP}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) = \sqrt{J_2(\boldsymbol{s})} + \eta(p_t - p) \quad (2.6)$$

where $\eta = \sqrt{2/3}M$ defines the slope of the outer edge of the cone. It should be noted that the capped Drucker-Prager prevents excessive plastic dilation and ensures yielding begins at critical state for highly overconsolidated soils. The associated flow rule at the Drucker-Prager cone is expressed as

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^p = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{J_2(\boldsymbol{s})}}\boldsymbol{s} + \frac{\eta}{3}\mathbf{I}. \quad (2.7)$$

The Drucker-Prager cone often predicts excessive dilatancy and a non-associate flow rule rule is used to correct for this. This differs from the associative flow rule only by replacing the volumetric component η with $\bar{\eta}$. The inner approximation of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion

$$\bar{\eta} = \frac{6 \sin \psi}{\sqrt{3}(3 - \sin \psi)}, \quad (2.8)$$

with the friction angle ϕ replaced by the dilatancy angle ψ of the Mohr-Coulomb yield surface [1].

FIGURE 2.3: Deviatoric stress over axial strain for three realisations of triaxial compression element tests with different overconsolidation ratios

FIGURE 2.4: Volumetric strain over axial strain for three realisations of triaxial compression element tests with different overconsolidation ratios

FIGURE 2.5: Deviatoric stress over pressure for three realisations of triaxial compression element tests with different overconsolidation ratios

FIGURE 2.6: Uniaxial compression showing the first principle stress over axial strain, and specific volume over pressure

2.2 $\mu(I)$ -rheology

The $\mu(I)$ rheology is a phenomenological model for homogeneous steady state shear flows of hard spherical particles. The model consists of three dimensionless quantities: the dynamic friction coefficient $\mu = \tau/p$, the solid volume fraction ϕ , and the inertial number I . Under shear without gravity, a homogeneous volume of particle experiences a variation in friction coefficient.

$$\mu(I) = \mu_s + \frac{\mu_d - \mu_s}{I_0/I + 1}, \quad (2.9)$$

where μ_s and μ_d is the friction coefficients associated with the Drucker-Prager Coulomb line and limit of the inertial regime, respectively. It should be noted that Eq 2.9 shows a singularity at $I = 0$, an alternative linearized version $\mu(I) \approx \mu_s + bI$ may be used for small I [2], where b is a fitting parameter. The inertial number is the ratio of the microscopic (particle-scale) relaxation time scale t_m related to the motion of a particle under an applied pressure, and t_γ is the macroscopic shear rate time scale $I = \frac{t_m}{t_\gamma}$. It takes on an expanded form

$$I = \frac{2d|\dot{\gamma}|}{\sqrt{\rho_p/p}}, \quad (2.10)$$

where d is the particle diameter, and ρ_p is the particle density. The quantity I_0 is a quantity associated with the limit of the validity of I^{**} . The brother of Eq 2.9 relates a decreasing monotonic solid volume fraction with the inertial number [2]

$$\phi(I) = \phi_c - aI, \quad (2.11)$$

where a is a fitting parameter, and ϕ_c is the solid volume fraction limit (jamming point) in the quasi-static regime. The dependence of I in Eq 2.9 can be replaced by rearranging 2.11, written as

$$I = \Psi(\phi) = \frac{\phi_c - \phi}{a}. \quad (2.12)$$

We are then able to derive the equation of state (EOS) for pressure with Eq 2.10 [2], such that

$$p = \rho_s \left(\frac{2d|\dot{\gamma}|}{\Psi(\phi)} \right)^2. \quad (2.13)$$

Bagnold scaling with the shear rate $p \sim |\dot{\gamma}|^2$ [3] is a direct consequence of dimensional analysis from the inertial number [2]. As the solid volume fraction approaches the jamming interface ϕ_c the pressure goes to infinity as ϕ which is problematic. A commonly used simplification of Eq. 2.13 involves assuming that granular flow is incompressible. A Bingham-like viscoplastic constitutive model is presented by [4] comprising the total stress tensor

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -p\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\tau}, \quad (2.14)$$

shear stress tensor

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \eta(\mu(I)) \frac{\dot{\gamma}_{ij}}{|\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}|}, \quad (2.15)$$

and granular viscosity

$$\eta(\mu(I)) = \mu(I)p. \quad (2.16)$$

A conjecture of Eq 2.15 is that the shear stress tensor is colinear with a shear strain rate and the material is always shearing ($|\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}| \neq 0$).

2.3 Best Practice Guidelines

Here we attempt to present best practices to modeling granular flow in solid-like and fluid like regimes.

2.3.1 modified Cam Clay

The modified Cam Clay is a solid-like rate independent soil mechanics model formulated for the stress dilatancy behaviour of clays. In general, the model works well for small pressure ranges [1], then linear isotropic elasticity may be acceptable. However, for large pressure ranges, a non-linear elastic law is required.

The shape of the yield surface also tends to overestimate the deviatoric stress for overconsolidated granular materials [5], [6]. The capped Drucker-Prager with a non-associative flow helps to correct the shape of the yield surface. The Drucker-Prager model by it self is not able to predict plastic compaction. The Drucker-Prager yield surface is a smooth approximation of the Mohr Coulomb yield surface, which is generally well suited for granular materials. Implementation of the capped Drucker-Prager can be done with a multi-surface model and the return mapping scheme, Newton Raphson [1].

Zhen-Yu et. al. also observes that the modified Cam Clay predicts unrealistically high K_0 value during isotropic or uniaxial compression. The hardening rule Eq ?? showed the possibility of giving negative specific volumes at low stresses, hence a new linear version of the hardening rule is preposed by [7].

2.3.2 $\mu(I)$ rheology

The $\mu(I)$ rheology, is a phenomenological model for homogeneous steady state granular flow of hard particles. The model exhibits several divergences: at zero shear strain rate (Eq 2.9 and 2.15), zero pressure (Eq 2.10) and at the critical solid volume fraction (Eq 2.13). Regularization methods are a numerical convenience to overcome these pain points, for example Papanastasiou's regularization for zero strain rate [8], [9] and regularization through compressibility [10]–[13].

In fact, Barker et. al. [13] showed that the incompressible $\mu(I)$ rheology [4] is ill-posed (Hadamard-type instability) nearby the quasi-static limits ($I = 0$ and $I = \infty$) and as a consequence, dependent on the grid resolution. Goddard et. al. [12] attributed the instability to the dissipation potential being marginally convex. They postulate that viscous or non-local may achieve regularization.

Indeed, predicting non-homogeneous flows from grain-scale boundary effects [14] is not possible for the (local) $\mu(I)$ rheology. Non-local models have been successful in capturing effects such as onset/stop of flow and silo clogging [15]–[17].

The formulation of $\mu(I)$ - rheology is limited by the condition of perfectly hard particles. That is, the microscopic relaxation time scale t_γ and the macroscopic shear rate time scale t_m are much greater than the contact time scale $t_c = \sqrt{\rho_s d^3/k}$. In the case of soft particles, the effects of interparticle frictions come to play. Vescovi et. al. [18] showed a significant deviation of $\mu(I)$ for deformable soft particles (large t_c) at low shear strain rate (low I). They further remarked, that softness of the particles and nonlocal effects are generally indistinguishable [18]. It is not possible for systems with perfectly rigid particles to undergo jammed shear flows. Several models, have formulated multi-regime models based on scaling relations of solid volume fraction and dimensionless shear rate [18], [19] and generalized rheology [20].

Finally, the alignment condition $\mu(I)$. Weinhart et. al. [21] showed from granular flow down an incline plane that the deviatoric stress tensor is slightly rotated against the shear stress. This is in discrepancy with the alignment condition Eq 2.15.

2.3.3 Unified model

We reflect on blending solid-like models and fluid-like models. There are several methods of merging the models. It is possible to derive an elasto-viscoplastic model with $\mu(I)$ rheology and soil mechanics (e.g. see Peric, Bingham, Perzyna definitions [1]). Its main difference from a rate independent implementation is that the plastic multiplier is an explicit function of stress, the rate terms are now actual time derivatives instead of increments (event sequences), and yield surfaces are allowed to be temporarily positive. The disadvantage of these methods are that

both models are integrated into a single implementation. Models may not be thermodynamic consistent which may lead to unphysical results and dissipation potentials is challenging to derive [22], [23]. On the other hand, one can choose to split the stress into a uncoupled quasi-static and inertial term (i.e. $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{qs} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{inert}$) [18], [19], [24]. The fluid-like term holds only if there is indeed, plastic flow.

We should clearly define the solid-fluid transition criterion. Then ensure that our models have appropriate scaling relations for the respective regimes under prescribed boundary conditions. For example, Chialvo et. al [19] performed a series of constant volume simple shear experiments with DEM. They defined the jamming point as the spike where there is a peak in pressure fluctuations. They presented a model that scales with the solid volume fraction and dimensionless shear rate for both above (jammed) and below (unjammed) the jamming point. As for the $\mu(I)$ -rheology [2], [4], one can only consider its contribution to the total stress when the material is in steady state flow.

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Chapter 3

DEM-Continuum coupling

3.1 Introduction

Discrete Element Methods (DEM) offer a high degree of accuracy but are computationally expensive when it comes to simulating large number of particles. The timestep chosen is significantly small when compared to continuum mechanics approach used for granular flows. Since small deformations need to be captured effectively during collisions, the stiffness of the material and the size of the particle influences the timestep chosen; these conditions often do not favour DEM simulations required in large scale industrial processes.

FIGURE 3.1: Funnel flow vs Mass flow showing different regions of mass flow and stagnation zones. Adopted from Url: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZYifIAtqsm>

Dense granular flows usually involve both areas of stagnation or mass flow and high-shear areas (as shown in Fig. 3.1); combining a continuum and a DEM model respectively for each area can significantly reduce simulation time. Dynamically switching between continuum and discrete regions within a simulation run can produce the most optimum simulation times.

3.2 DEM-FEM coupling

One of the most common methods of coupling FEM and DEM is through surface coupling. Surface coupling can be used to simulate interactions between particles and deformable objects [25]–[27], while ‘Volume coupling’ is suitable for simulating granular particles as a continuous bulk material [28]–[30]. DEM can be used in areas of high shear or relative motion and the FEM can handle regions of quasi-static deformations.

FIGURE 3.2: Adopted from [28]. Both methods are superposed within the overlapping domain where the virtual work is interpolated using the weight function $w(\mathbf{x})$

In volume coupling (also known as the Arlequin framework [31], [32]), the different computational models are coupled together within an overlapping volume by applying kinematic constraints on their solutions and weighting the governing equations based on the partition of unity (refer to Fig. 3.2). The Arlequin coupling is completed through the imposition of kinematic constraints within the overlapping volume. For the coupling of a discrete particle and a continuum method the formulation of appropriate constraints is not straightforward. The particles are equipped with translational and rotational degrees of freedom (DOF). A standard continuum approach is applied without rotational DOFs in FEM domain because it is sufficient for the description of the material behavior when no localizations occur. Therefore, constraints will only be formulated in terms of the translational DOFs.

3.2.1 Governing equations

The deformation of a body can be described by the principle of virtual displacements, Eq.(3.1) shows the virtual work formulation used in FEM, where the density of the undeformed body, ρ , the body force density \mathbf{b} acting on the domain Ω , and the surface traction \mathbf{t} acting on a subset of the body’s boundary, $\Gamma_{\mathbf{t}} \subset \partial\Omega^{\text{FE}}$ describe the continuum. The stress and strain tensors $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ represent a work conjugate pair, and $\delta\mathbf{X}$ and $\delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ denote virtual variations of the position

vector and strain tensor. Eq.(3.2) shows the translational equations of motion used in DEM, where the force \mathbf{f}_α^b acts at the position \mathbf{x}_α and $\mathbf{f}_{\alpha\beta}$ represents the contact forces at $\mathbf{x}_{\alpha\beta}^c$, where $\beta = 1, \dots, N_\alpha$ denote the contact partners of particle $\alpha = 1, \dots, N_p$.

$$\int_{\Omega^{\text{FE}}} \left\{ \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \left(\mathbf{b} - \rho \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{X}}{\partial t^2} \right) \cdot \delta \mathbf{X} \right\} dV - \int_{\Gamma_t} \mathbf{t} \cdot \delta \mathbf{X} dA = 0, \quad (3.1)$$

$$m_\alpha \frac{d\mathbf{v}_\alpha}{dt} - \mathbf{f}_\alpha^b - \sum_{\beta=1}^{N_\alpha} \mathbf{f}_{\alpha\beta} = 0, \quad (3.2)$$

3.2.2 Hybrid coupling formulation

The volume coupling method, also known as the Arlequin framework for multi-model coupling, is a Lagrange multiplier or penalty-based approach that enforces kinematic constraints in an overlapping domain Ω^C . The virtual work within the coupled system can be described as shown in Eq.(3.3). The virtual work is equal to the weighted sum of the work done by the sub-models, which can be expressed as $\delta W = \delta W^{\text{FE}} + \delta W^{\text{DE}}$. To weight the virtual work done in the DEM model δW^{DE} , a smooth and continuous function $w(\mathbf{x})$ of the particle position $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega^C$ is used. This function increases monotonically from zero on $\partial\Omega^{\text{FE}} \cap \Omega^C$ to one on $\partial\Omega^{\text{DE}} \cap \Omega^C$. The virtual work done in the FEM model δW^{FE} is weighted by the function $1 - w(\mathbf{X})$, such that the coupling weights on the FEM and DEM sides sum to unity at any given location. The coupled governing equations are also adjusted by the corresponding coupling weights. In the equations shown, N_e and N_r are the total numbers of volume and surface elements in Ω and Γ_t , respectively, and N_p is the total number of discrete particles. The short-hand notation $w_\alpha = w(\mathbf{x}_\alpha)$ and $w_{\alpha\beta} = w(\mathbf{x}_{\alpha\beta}^c)$ is used for the weights at the particle positions and contact points. $\delta \mathbf{x}_\alpha$ is a variation of the position of particle α . The terms \mathbf{b}^C and \mathbf{f}_α^C describes the FEM coupling force density and the DEM coupling force respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} \delta W = & \int_{\Omega^{\text{FE}}} (1 - w) \left\{ \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \left(\mathbf{b} - \rho \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{X}}{\partial t^2} \right) \cdot \delta \mathbf{X} \right\} dV + \int_{\Gamma_t^{\text{FE}}} \mathbf{t} \cdot \delta \mathbf{X} dA + \int_{\Omega^{\text{FE}}} \mathbf{b}^C \cdot \delta \mathbf{X} dV \\ & + \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_p} \left[w_\alpha \left(m_\alpha \frac{d^2 \mathbf{x}_\alpha}{dt^2} - \mathbf{f}_\alpha^b \right) \cdot \delta \mathbf{x}_\alpha - \sum_{\beta}^{N_\alpha} w_{\alpha\beta} \mathbf{f}_{\alpha\beta} \cdot \delta \mathbf{x}_\alpha \right] - \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_p} \mathbf{f}_\alpha^C \cdot \delta \mathbf{x}_\alpha, \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\mathbf{b}^C = \epsilon(\mathbf{u}^{\text{DE}} - \mathbf{u}^{\text{FE}}), \quad (3.4)$$

$$\mathbf{f}_\alpha^C = -\epsilon \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \Pi_{i\alpha} \int_{\Omega^C} \psi_i \psi_j dV (\mathbf{u}_j^{\text{DE}} - \mathbf{u}_j^{\text{FE}}). \quad (3.5)$$

3.3 Results

3.3.1 1D force transfer problem

To verify the volume coupling, a primary check is to ensure whether the hybrid system reaches an equilibrium with the right amount force transferring between DEM and FEM. To test this, a column of granular particles contained in a frictionless container has been modelled with the hybrid approach. The hybrid modelling consists of 3 different zones as shown in the Fig.3.3. There exists a total of 8 elements in which 4 of them are in the pure FEM zone and the other 4 are in the hybrid zone. Each element in the hybrid zone contains 8 DEM particles, arranged in a cubic packing fashion. A linearly increasing compressive load up to 0.1N is applied slowly on top nodes of the pure FEM zone. The verification involves equating the force with the reaction from the base as well as ensuring proper transfer of loads from FEM to DEM in the hybrid zone. It has also been verified that the force balance is achieved when the domain is flipped vertically, i.e force is applied from the DEM zone.

To ensure uniform material behaviour, the effective stiffness and density of the DEM and FEM systems were matched. A relation was established between the Young's modulus of the continuum zone and the stiffness of the particles by calculating the effective stiffness of the column using individual particle stiffness. Since the loading is purely in the vertical direction and the particles are arranged on top of each other confined in a frictionless container, the horizontal forces are negligible and hence the poisson's ratio in continuum is kept 0. The full list of properties is as shown in Table 3.1 and the DEM properties are listed in Table 3.2.

Figure 3.4 shows the comparison of the applied force and their affect on the forces generated at the coupling zone. The 'nodal coupling forces' refers to the sum of forces generated in the hybrid zone which are acting on the nodes of FEM elements. The 'base reaction' is measured as the force experienced by the bottom wall of the container. It can be seen that all the forces converge to the value of the applied force after a short delay; this is due to the inertial effects of the system and coupling forces being computed as a function of the difference in displacement between FEM and DEM systems.

FIGURE 3.3: Schematic of the test problem setup showing the FEM domain, DEM domain, and the DEM-FEM hybrid domain along with their respective dimensions.

TABLE 3.1: FEM Properties

Property	Value
Solver type	Dynamic
Constitutive law	Linear Elastic
Rayleigh alpha damping	200 s^{-1}
Young's modulus	$500,000 \text{ N/m}^2$
Poisson's ratio	0
Density	1312.5 kg/m^3
Analysis type	Nonlinear
Timestep	10^{-5} s
Penalty parameter	10^8 Pa/m^2

To verify proper transfer of loads from FEM to DEM, the stresses developed within the FEM elements were measured. Figure 3.5 shows the value of compressive stresses developed inside each element. The elements are number 1 to 8 from top to bottom. The hybrid zone consists of elements 5 to 8. It was observed that a change in penalty parameter affects the stress distribution within the hybrid zone. A larger penalty parameter indicates a stiffer coupling between the DEM and FEM zones, although this leads undesired stress distribution. A penalty parameter which is too small is not suitable for coupling since this will force the DEM and FEM systems to maintain a larger displacement difference causing greater mismatch in displacements with the ground truth DEM simulations. A penalty parameter of 10^8 is observed to be ideal for the element size used in this problem.

On the DEM side, it was observed that the load gets added to the particles in the hybrid zone

TABLE 3.2: DEM Properties

Property	Value
Diameter of particle	0.01 m
Solver type	Spring dashpot model
Particle density	2500 kg/m ³
K_normal	5000 N/m
Coefficient of Restitution (COR)	0.1
Timestep	10 ⁻⁵ s
Penalty parameter	10 ⁸ Pa/m ²

FIGURE 3.4: Shows the comparison of the magnitude of applied load, nodal coupling forces, and the reaction from the base.

FIGURE 3.5: Shows the comparison of the magnitude of applied load, nodal coupling forces, and the reaction from the base.

in a cumulative fashion as shown in Fig. 3.6. Each layer shown in the Fig. 3.7 is situated at the centers of the FEM elements in the hybrid zone. The last layer is contained outside the hybrid zone. It can be observed that this layer bears the complete load applied. This verifies a smooth load transfer from FEM to DEM zone.

FIGURE 3.6: Shows the comparison of the magnitude of applied load, nodal coupling forces, and the reaction from the base.

FIGURE 3.7: Image demonstrating the location of each layer

3.3.2 3D force transfer problem

Modelling granular flow using FEM involves calibrating the parameters used in the constitutive relations from the ground truth (DEM) simulations. For an isotropic linear elastic constitutive model there are 2 elastic constants that need to be calibrated; they are Poisson ratio and Elastic modulus. These can be calibrated by performing compression tests using pure DEM simulations. Also the bulk density of the ground truth DEM particles needs to match with the density of the FEM material specification. In this article, the DEM particles are given a high coefficient of friction to replicate elastic behaviour. In general, granular flow exhibits plasticity when slips occur between each particle. For future works that include plasticity in the FEM models, more parameters must be calibrated with the ground truth DEM simulation. Hybrid simulation results for this case are not included with this article.

3.3.2.1 Model parameters to calibrate

For an isotropic linear elastic model, the Bulk density, Poisson ratio and Elastic Modulus need to be obtained from the ground truth DEM simulations.

3.3.2.2 Ground truth DEM simulation set-up used

The ground truth DEM simulation setup is shown in Fig. 3.8. Domain size : 0.06m (length) x 0.06m (breadth) x 0.12m (height). Particles are placed in a rigid frictionless container. A moving plate with constrained motion in the x, y and z directions is used to exert force on the

top of the particles. The plate moves with a constant velocity in the negative y direction and is constrained not to rotate about x, y, and z axes nor move in x and z directions.

FIGURE 3.8: Simulation setup

3.3.2.3 Procedure

The compression test is done by a stepwise approach as follows:

1. Particles are settled in gravity and collected in the container.
2. Particles are slowly compressed by a small force and then slowly released. Particle-Particle contacts are assumed to be frictionless in this process.
3. In the final step, the particles are slowly compressed with a linearly increasing load ranging from 0 to 5N. After the 5N is achieved the simulation stops. In this case, maximum friction is used Coefficient of friction =2 to avoid slipping and replicate elastic behaviour.

3.3.2.4 Calculation of isotropic linear elastic constants

Assuming vertical loading ,the isotropic linear elastic equations can be written as:

$$\varepsilon_{xx} = \frac{1}{E} [\sigma_{xx} - \nu(\sigma_{yy} + \sigma_{zz})] \quad (3.6)$$

$$\varepsilon_{yy} = \frac{1}{E} [\sigma_{yy} - \nu(\sigma_{xx} + \sigma_{zz})] \quad (3.7)$$

For a rigid container, we assume $\sigma_{xx} = \sigma_{zz}$ and $\varepsilon_{xx} = \varepsilon_{zz} = 0$.

From Eq.(4),

$$0 = -\nu\sigma_{yy} + (1 - \nu)\sigma_{xx} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{xx}}{\sigma_{yy}} = \frac{\nu}{1 - \nu} \quad (3.9)$$

Assigning $\frac{\sigma_{xx}}{\sigma_{yy}} = k$, we get poisson ratio:

$$\nu = \frac{k}{1 + k} \quad (3.10)$$

From Eq.(5) , using $\sigma_{xx} = k\sigma_{yy}$ and $\sigma_{xx} = \sigma_{zz}$,

$$E\varepsilon_{yy} = \sigma_{yy} - 2\nu k\sigma_{yy} \quad (3.11)$$

$$E = (1 - 2\nu k) \frac{\sigma_{yy}}{\varepsilon_{yy}} \quad (3.12)$$

From the compaction test result, using the vertical stress vs strain graph (Fig.3.9) and the horizontal vs vertical stress graph (Fig.3.10), we can get the ratios k and $\frac{\sigma_{yy}}{\varepsilon_{yy}}$ which can be used to find the poisson ratio and Elastic modulus as described in Eq.(3.10),(3.12). The results are tabulated in Table. 3.3. A further comparison of FEM and DEM simulation is shown in Fig. 3.11 and Fig. 3.12. Although the two graphs maintain the same ratio for DEM and FEM cases, they do not overlap with each other; this is due to the misposition of the plate that was used to compress the particles in the pure DEM case. In absence of gravity, a minor mispositioning is expected since the particles tend to expand out in zero stress state.

TABLE 3.3: Properties of DEM and FEM

Properties of DEM		Properties of FEM	
Diameter of particle	0.005 m (avg)	Solver type	Dynamic, implicit
Particle distribution	Normal distribution	Young's modulus	53.783 KPa
Particle dia range	0.002m to 0.000814m	Rayleigh alpha damping coef.	200 kg/s
Solver type	Spring dashpot model	Poisson's ratio	0.248
Particle density	2500 kg/m ³	Density	1551.26 kg/m ³
K_normal	5000 N/m	Analysis type	Non-linear
K_tangential	5000 N/m	Timestep	10 ⁻⁶ s
K_normal with wall	50000 N/m		
COR	0.1		
COF	2		
Timestep	10 ⁻⁶ s		

FIGURE 3.9: Showing horizontal vs vertical stress. Lateral stress ratio = 0.33 . Calculation is done on the last 60% of the values on the plot. Lateral stress ratio $k = \Delta$ horizontal stress / Δ vertical stress.

FIGURE 3.10: Stress vs strain. (Stress/s-train) ratio = 64309.13 Pa. Calculation is done on the last 60% of the values on the plot. Calculation of slope = Δ vertical stress / Δ strain.

FIGURE 3.11: Comparison of lateral stress ratios: DEM = 0.33, FEM = 0.33.

FIGURE 3.12: Comparison of stress strain ratios: DEM = 64309.13 Pa, FEM = 64301.02 Pa.

3.4 Summary

This article has presented a comprehensive overview of the integration of Discrete Element Methods (DEM) with Finite Element Methods (FEM) to simulate granular flows in a computationally efficient manner. Given the challenges posed by the computational expense of simulating large numbers of particles using DEM alone, the coupling with FEM offers a promising approach to model complex granular flows encountered in industrial processes.

Key to the success of this method is the careful calibration of model parameters to ensure that the material behavior in the DEM and FEM models is consistent. The 1D and 3D force transfer problems illustrated in this article demonstrate the validity of the hybrid model, showing that forces and stresses can be accurately transferred between the DEM and FEM domains. These examples underscore the importance of selecting appropriate penalty parameters and matching

the material properties between the DEM particles and the FEM domain to achieve realistic and reliable simulation results.

By addressing the computational challenges associated with DEM simulations and leveraging the strengths of FEM for modeling quasi-static deformations, the hybrid DEM-FEM approach represents a significant advancement in the simulation of granular flows. This methodology not only enhances the accuracy of simulations but also makes it feasible to model large-scale industrial processes involving granular materials. Future work will likely focus on further refining the coupling techniques, improving the efficiency of simulations, and expanding the applicability of the hybrid model to a wider range of granular flow problems.

3.5 Best Practice Guidelines

Researching and developing the hybrid DEM-FEM approach for simulating granular flows has underscored several effective research practices that are instrumental in the success of interdisciplinary and computational research projects. This section reflects on these practices, highlighting how they have been applied in the context of this study and providing insights for future research endeavors.

The integration of DEM and FEM methodologies necessitates expertise from computational mechanics, materials science, and software engineering. Effective collaboration among experts from these disciplines was pivotal. It facilitated a comprehensive understanding of both granular flow physics and computational techniques, enabling the development of a robust and efficient hybrid simulation approach. Regular interdisciplinary meetings and shared documentation platforms fostered effective communication and knowledge exchange.

Adapting existing methods and innovating new solutions were key to overcoming the research challenges. The development of the volume coupling method, based on the Arlequin framework, involved creative problem-solving to formulate appropriate constraints and weight functions that could seamlessly integrate DEM and FEM models within a unified simulation framework.

The credibility of the hybrid DEM-FEM approach hinges on rigorous validation and verification processes. This involved designing detailed test cases, such as the 1D and 3D force transfer problems, to systematically verify the force and stress transfer mechanisms between DEM and FEM domains. Additionally, calibrating the model parameters against ground truth DEM simulations ensures that the hybrid model accurately represents the physical behavior of granular flows.

Representing granular particles with continuum models presents significant challenges in achieving the accuracy comparable to that of the Discrete Element Method (DEM), primarily due to

DEM's capacity to embody a broader spectrum of degrees of freedom. This advantage stems from DEM's Lagrangian framework, which meticulously accounts for the motion of individual particles. Nevertheless, it is feasible to delineate the circumstances under which continuum models can validly represent granular materials. Such conditions are predominantly observed in quasi-static granular motions. For a continuum model to effectively approximate granular behavior as represented by DEM, it is imperative to meticulously define all pertinent boundary conditions, stress states, material density, stiffness, and additional parameters critical to the chosen constitutive model. This comprehensive specification facilitates the establishment of a robust coupling between DEM and continuum models for an accurate representation of the same granular material.

The rapidly evolving field of computational simulation demands continuous learning and skill development. Engaging with the latest research literature, attending workshops and conferences, and peer learning within the research team were essential for staying updated with recent advancements. This ongoing learning process not only enriched the research project but also fostered personal and professional growth.

Feedback from research team, presentations, and discussions with experts was invaluable. It provided critical insights that led to iterative improvements in the hybrid model. Embracing constructive criticism and being open to revising assumptions and methodologies were crucial for refining the research outcomes.

Given the complexity and multidisciplinary nature of the research, effective project management was essential. This involved setting clear milestones, managing timelines, and allocating resources efficiently. Utilizing project management tools and agile methodologies helped in keeping the project on track and adapting to evolving research needs.

In conclusion, the successful development of the hybrid DEM-FEM approach for simulating granular flows was underpinned by a combination of interdisciplinary collaboration, methodological innovation, and rigorous validation. These insights into effective research practices not only facilitated the current project but also offer valuable guidance for future research endeavors in computational science and engineering.

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Chapter 4

CFD-DEM magnification lens

4.1 Introduction

Fluid-particle flows (i.e., particle-laden flows) are common in environmental flows such as sediment transport and volcanic eruption, and many engineering applications, including, pneumatic conveying, fluidized beds, spouted beds and risers. The presence of dispersed phase (particle phase) gives rise to a broad range of length and time scales that needs to be considered in the modelling of such flows. In addition, the large separation of scales observed in the particle laden flows, wherein processes happen at the microscale, such as particle collisions and fluid-particle interactions, affect the structures at the macroscale, poses a challenge to the modeling of these flows [1]. Therefore, a multiscale modelling strategy which can model the fluid-particle flows at different time and length scales with different levels of detail is needed [2].

Three main multiscale modelling approaches are: particle-resolved direct numerical simulation (PR-DNS), Euler-Lagrange models (e.g., unresolved computational fluid dynamics coupled with discrete element method, unresolved CFD-DEM or CFD-DEM), and Euler-Euler models (e.g., two-fluid model, TFM) [3]. The PR-DNS method is the most detailed method to model particle-laden flows, since it can resolve all the time and length scales of both phases. At the intermediate level of accuracy of multiscale modelling approaches, lies the CFD-DEM model. The particles are tracked individually, while a grid size larger than particle diameter is employed to model the fluid phase using locally averaged Navier-Stokes equations. The least detailed method is the TFM approach, where the fluid phase is modelled in the same manner as CFD-DEM model and the locally averaged Navier-Stokes type equations are applied to resolve the particle phase. In other words, both phases are treated as interpenetrating continua. In both TFM and CFD-DEM approaches, the two-way coupling between the phases is achieved through fluid-particle interaction force closures.

The significantly high computational resources required by the PR-DNS model, hinders it from being applied to simulate systems with relatively high number of particles. Instead, the PR-DNS model is commonly adopted to study the microscale flow features and particularly it has turned to a tool to derive interphase momentum [4]–[6] and heat [7], [8] exchange closures for less accurate models, e.g., CFD-DEM and TFM approaches. The CFD-DEM model is less computationally demanding compared to the PR-DNS model and particle-particle and particle-wall interactions can be captured precisely using the physical models such as soft-sphere [9] or hard-sphere [10] models. Resolving particle-particle and particle-wall contacts increases the computational time of CFD-DEM simulations, which limits their application in simulating systems with more than a few million particles unless a huge computational resource is utilized [11]. Despite the enhanced accessibility to supercomputers and their exceptional computational power, the capabilities of CFD-DEM simulations remain inadequate for industrial applications for which the system may contain trillions of particles. Meanwhile, the TFM model requires less computational cost, but, its accuracy is lower than CFD-DEM model, since it is strongly connected to the particle phase transport coefficients and constitutive relations used in the TFM model. The TFM model is classified into, (1) fine grid TFM approach with high resolution, and (2) coarse grid TFM approaches like filtered-TFM [12] and spatially-averaged TFM [13]. In addition, the TFM model is preferable to simulate the large-scale fluid-particle systems.

There are multiple studies regarding comparing the performance and computational efficiency of the CFD-DEM and the TFM approaches in fluid-particle systems such as fluidized beds [14], [15], spouted beds [16], [17], and spout fluidized beds [18], [19]. All studies have reported that the CFD-DEM exhibits a superior level of accuracy compared to the TFM, while this enhanced accuracy comes at the cost of increased computational demand. Furthermore, the findings indicate that the success of TFM model depends on constitutive closures for kinetic-collisional and frictional solids stresses, as well as particle-wall interactions [18]. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully select the TFM model parameters.

The similarities between PR-DNS and Euler-Lagrange methods in treating the particle phase, and Euler-Lagrange and Euler-Euler approaches in treating the fluid phase and the momentum exchange closures has led to develop of hybrid multiscale modelling approaches. These models try to simultaneously take advantage of accuracy of the detailed models and less computational demands of the less accurate model. The hybrid multiscale models are developed in such a way that concurrently combine a detailed model with a less accurate one like the PR-DNS with the CFD-DEM [20] or the continuum coupled with the discrete method [21], [22]. The framework of the concurrent hybrid multiscale models available in the literature for the fluid-particle flows can be divided into two categories: (1) "shared domain" approach which both models are existing in the whole simulation domain (2) "domain decomposition" approach which the detailed model is applied in a small portion of the domain to improve the predictions of the less accurate model

and both models exchange information through a shared reconciliation grid layer and/or a shared boundary.

The hybrid multiscale models using the "shared domain" approach are common in the literature [23]–[26]. For instance, Schneiderbauer et al. [27] used a hybrid coarse-grid TFM-DPM model to simulate an industrial-scale cyclone with poly-disperse particles. The coupling between the models was achieved by determining the local Sauter mean diameter from DPM tracers and subsequently applying it to the coarse-grid TFM to evaluate the local drag force (DPM to the coarse-grid TFM step) and using the particle phase stress field from the coarse-grid TFM to obtain the particle-particle contact force in the DPM using a solid-solid drag (coarse-grid TFM to DPM step). Using this hybrid model, they could correctly predict the fractional separation of sub-micrometer particles in the cyclone. A hybrid TFM-DEM model was utilized by Yin et al. [25] to study the particle segregation in a coal beneficiation fluidized bed. The TFM model was used to treat the dense solid phase (fine particles) and the dilute solid phase (i.e, the beneficiated coal particles (coarse particles)) was modelled using the DEM. The particle-particle and particle-wall interactions of dilute solid phase was handled using soft-sphere method. The coupling between the models was obtained by incorporating a source term in the momentum equation of the TFM particle phase, which accounted for the influence of discrete particles through solid-solid drag. Similarly, the momentum equation of the discrete particles was also modified by the inclusion of the same force source term. They studied the segregation mechanisms using their hybrid TFM-DEM model and observed that a reduction in the size of discrete particles resulted in a drop in the degree of segregation.

There are a very limited number of studies that has used the "domain decomposition" framework in the hybrid modelling of fluid-particle flows. Chen et al. [22], [28]–[30] developed a hybrid model to concurrently couple the TFM with the CFD-DEM where the same fluid phase was used for both models. They applied the CFD-DEM in the vicinity of the channel walls to resolve the particle-wall interactions whereas the TFM was implemented in the central region of the channel. Also, the TFM and the CFD-DEM regions only overlapped in the reconciliation layer where they were exchanging information. They conducted a comparative analysis of the predictions obtained from three different models: the CFD-DEM, the TFM, and the hybrid models in terms of the time-averaged void fraction profiles, the time-averaged solids and fluid velocity profiles. The findings suggest that the hybrid model can improve the accuracy of the TFM predictions, resulting in a closer agreement with the CFD-DEM predictions.

The emergence of a novel hybrid multiscale modelling methodology within the domain decomposition framework, integrating the TFM and CFD-DEM methods, gives rise to the following questions: (1) Can a hybrid model be implemented in a specific region of interest in the TFM simulation and magnify the continuum particle phase with discrete particles? (2) Is it feasible to develop a hybrid approach capable of simulating the heterogeneous instabilities observed in

particle-laden flows, by using information from the continuum model? (3) Is it possible to create a hybrid model that can modify the non-physical behavior of the TFM to conform to physical behavior?

In this paper, we try to answer the questions asked above, with introducing a new hybrid multiscale model based on the domain decomposition framework. This hybrid model applies a CFD-DEM approach within a specific region of interest in a TFM simulation. In the boundaries of the region, the information from the TFM is used to initialize and derive the CFD-DEM simulations while in a region away from the boundaries, the CFD-DEM affects the TFM simulation.

In this work, we will examine the effectiveness of our developed hybrid multiscale method, in case of particle jets and unbounded fluidization simulations. Also, the results of the CFD-DEM simulations will be adopted as the ground truth to validate the TFM and the new hybrid multiscale method.

4.2 Numerical approaches

4.2.1 TFM

The locally averaged mass and momentum equations for the fluid and the continuum particle phases are written as [31], [32],

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_q \rho_q) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_q \rho_q \mathbf{u}_q) = \Omega_{cp} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{u}_f) = -\alpha_f \nabla p_f + \alpha_f \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f - \beta_{TFM} (\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{cp}) + \alpha_f \rho_f \mathbf{g} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp}) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp}) = -\alpha_{cp} \nabla p_f - \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{S}_{cp}^{kc} + \mathbf{S}_{cp}^{fr}) + \beta_{TFM} (\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{cp}) + \alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{g} + \boldsymbol{\Psi}_{cp} \quad (4.3)$$

where in Eq. (4.1), \mathbf{u}_q , α_q and ρ_q are the velocity, volume fraction and density of the phase q , where q represents either the continuum particle phase or the fluid phase, $q = cp, f$. The variable Ω_{cp} in Eq. (4.1) represents a semi-implicit source which will be discussed in section 4.2.4. The fluid phase pressure is p_f . A Newtonian deviatoric stress is considered for the fluid phase stress-strain tensor, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_f$ which is,

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_f = 2\mu_f \left(\frac{1}{2} (\nabla \mathbf{u}_f + \nabla \mathbf{u}_f^T) - \frac{1}{3} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_f \mathbf{I} \right) \quad (4.4)$$

Also, \mathbf{S}_{cp}^{kc} and \mathbf{S}_{cp}^{fr} are the kinetic-collisional solids stress and the frictional solids stress tensors, respectively. The frictional solids stress tensor is closed using a normal frictional solids stress and

a $\mu(I)$ -rheology models proposed by Chialvo et al. [33]. The frictional solids stress is considered when $\alpha_{cp} \gtrsim 0.4$. It should be noted that our previous paper [18] provided a comprehensive explanation of the Chialvo et al. [33] frictional solids stress model. Hence, interested readers can refer to that particular study. In addition, β_{TFM} denotes the interphase momentum exchange coefficient in the TFM approach. The variable Ψ_{cp} in Eq. (4.3) denotes a semi-implicit source term described further below in section 4.2.4. Table 4.1 represents the constitutive relations for the TFM approach used in this paper.

The dependency of the kinetic-collisional solids stress on the continuum particle phase velocity fluctuations, leads to supplement of the continuum particle phase locally averaged mass and momentum equations with a balance of pseudo-thermal energy (PTE), as shown in Eq. (4.5), where granular temperature is defined as, $\Theta = 2/3E_{PT}$. To close the kinetic-collisional solids stress tensor shown in Eq. (4.6), solids pressure, p_{cp}^{kc} , and bulk viscosity, λ_{cp}^{kc} , represented in Eq. (4.13) are necessary. The first term at the RHS of Eq. (4.5) denotes generation of the PTE due to the kinetic-collisional solids shear, the second term represents the diffusion of the PTE, the third term and the fourth terms are accounting for the transfer of kinetic energy of the continuum particle phase velocity fluctuations to the fluid phase. Finally, the fifth term is rate of dissipation of the PTE due to the inelastic particle collisions. The boundary conditions for the solid shear stresses, τ_{cp}^{kc} , and the outward flux of the fluctuation energy, $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{q}$, in wall-bounded simulations were implemented based on the work of Schneiderbauer et al. [34]. The total wall shear stress, τ_{cp} , is comprised of the kinetic-collisional shear stress and the frictional shear stress, τ_{cp}^{fr} . For detailed explanations about the TFM constitutive relations, refer to our previous paper [18].

4.2.2 CFD-DEM

The idea of our hybrid multiscale modelling which will be discussed further below requires to use a mutual fluid phase between TFM and CFD-DEM approaches and not to solve the momentum equation of the fluid phase in the CFD-DEM simulations. Therefore, here, we only discuss the momentum balance for the discrete particle phase based on a soft-sphere DEM approach,

$$m_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_{dp,i}}{dt} = \sum_{i \neq j}^n \mathbf{F}_i^{contact} + \mathbf{F}_i^{f-dp} + \mathbf{F}_i^g \quad (4.18)$$

where m_i and $\mathbf{u}_{dp,i}$ are the particle mass and the particle translational velocity, respectively. In addition, $\mathbf{F}_i^{contact}$ are the particle-particle collisions of surrounding particles j on particle i and particle-wall interactions described by non-linear Hertzian spring dashpot model [35] which normal and tangential contact forces are presented in Table 4.2. Furthermore, \mathbf{F}_i^g is the gravitational body force acting on the particle i and particle-fluid interaction forces, \mathbf{F}_i^{f-dp} , considered are,

$$\mathbf{F}_i^{f-dp} = \mathbf{F}_{drag,i} + \mathbf{F}_{\nabla p_f,i} + \mathbf{F}_{\nabla \cdot \tau_f,i} \quad (4.19)$$

TABLE 4.1: Constitutive relations of TFM momentum equation [18]

Pseudo-thermal energy equation:

$$\frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \Theta) + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp} \Theta) \right) = -\mathbf{S}_{cp}^{\text{kc}} : \nabla \mathbf{u}_{cp} - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} + \Gamma_{cp} - J_v - \gamma_{\Theta} \quad (4.5)$$

Kinetic-collisional solids stress tensor:

$$\mathbf{S}_{cp}^{\text{kc}} = \left(P_{cp}^{\text{kc}} - \lambda_{cp}^{\text{kc}} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D}_{cp}) \right) \mathbf{I} - 2\mu_{cp}^{\text{kc}} \text{dev} \mathbf{D}_{cp}, \quad \mathbf{D}_{cp} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\nabla \mathbf{u}_{cp} + (\nabla \mathbf{u}_{cp})^T \right), \quad \text{dev} \mathbf{D}_{cp} = \mathbf{D}_{cp} - \frac{1}{3} \text{tr}(\mathbf{D}_{cp}) \mathbf{I} \quad (4.6)$$

Solids viscosity:

$$\mu_{cp}^{\text{kc}} = \left(\frac{2 + \alpha'}{3} \right) \left\{ \frac{\mu^*}{g_0 \eta_{cp} (2 - \eta_{cp})} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{l_{cp}}{\mathbb{L}}} + \frac{8}{5} \alpha_{cp} \eta_{cp} g_0 \right) \left(1 + \frac{8}{5} \eta_{cp} (3\eta_{cp} - 2) \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) + \frac{3}{5} \eta_{cp} \mu_b \right\} \quad (4.7)$$

$$\mu^* = \frac{\mu}{1 + \frac{2\beta_{TFM}\mu}{(\alpha_{cp}\rho_{cp})^2 g_0 \Theta}}, \quad \mu = \frac{5\rho_{cp} d_{cp} \sqrt{\pi\Theta}}{96}, \quad \mu_b = \frac{256\mu\alpha_{cp}^2 g_0}{5\pi}, \quad \alpha' = \frac{8}{5}, \quad \eta_{cp} = \frac{1}{2} (1 + e_{cp-w}), \quad l_{cp} = \frac{d_{cp}}{6\sqrt{2}g_0\alpha_{cp}}. \quad (4.8)$$

Radial distribution function:

$$g_0 = \frac{1}{1 - \min(\alpha_{cp}, \alpha_{cp}^{\text{min}}) / \alpha_{cp}^{\text{max}}} \quad (4.9)$$

Pseudo-thermal energy (PTE) flux vector \mathbf{q} , rate of dissipation of PTE γ_{Θ} , rate of dissipation of PTE by viscous damping J_v and rate of production of PTE by fluid-particle slip Γ_{cp} :

$$\mathbf{q} = -\frac{\kappa^*}{g_0} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{l_{cp}}{\mathbb{L}}} + \frac{12}{5} \eta_{cp} \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) + \left(1 + \frac{12}{5} \eta_{cp}^2 (4\eta_{cp} - 3) \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) + \frac{64}{25\pi} (41 - 33\eta_{cp}) \eta_{cp}^2 \alpha_{cp}^2 g_0^2 \right\} \nabla \Theta, \quad (4.10)$$

$$\gamma_{\Theta} = \frac{48}{\sqrt{\pi}} \eta_{cp} (1 - \eta_{cp}) \frac{\rho_{cp} \alpha_{cp}^2}{d_{cp}} g_0 \Theta^{3/2}, \quad \kappa^* = \frac{\kappa}{1 + \frac{6\beta_{TFM}\kappa}{5(\alpha_{cp}\rho_{cp})^2 g_0 \Theta}}, \quad \kappa = \frac{75\rho_{cp} d_{cp} \sqrt{\pi\Theta}}{48\eta_{cp} (41 - 33\eta_{cp})}, \quad (4.11)$$

$$\Gamma_{cp} = \frac{d_{cp} \beta_{TFM}^2 \|\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{cp}\|^2}{4\alpha_{cp} g_0 \rho_{cp} \sqrt{\pi\Theta}}, \quad J_v = 3\beta\Theta \quad (4.12)$$

solids pressure and bulk viscosity:

$$p_{cp}^{\text{kc}} = \alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{l_{cp}}{\mathbb{L}}} + 4\eta_{cp} \alpha_{cp} g_0 \right) \Theta, \quad \lambda_{cp}^{\text{kc}} = \frac{8}{3} \eta_{cp} \alpha_{cp}^2 \rho_{cp} d_{cp} g_0 \sqrt{\frac{\Theta}{\pi}} \quad (4.13)$$

Boundary conditions for solid phase:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{kc}} = -\eta_w \mu_w \alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} g_0 \Theta \text{erf}(\bar{u}_{cp}) \frac{\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{\text{sl}}}{\|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{\text{sl}}\|}, \quad \mu_0 = \frac{7}{2} \frac{1 + e_{cp-w}}{1 + \beta_0} \mu_w, \quad \eta_w = \frac{1}{2} (1 + e_{cp-w}), \quad \bar{u}_{cp} = \frac{\|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{\text{sl}}\|}{\sqrt{2\Theta\mu_0}}, \quad (4.14)$$

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{q} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{kc}} \cdot \mathbf{u}_{cp}^{\text{sl}} - \frac{\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} g_0 \eta_w \sqrt{\Theta}}{\sqrt{2\mu_0^2 \sqrt{\pi}}} \exp(-\bar{u}_{cp}^2) \left\{ \mu_w \left[2\mu_w \|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{\text{sl}}\|^2 (2\eta_w - \mu_0) + \Theta (14\mu_w \eta_w - 4\mu_0 (1 + \mu_w) - 6\mu_w \mu_0^2 \eta_w) \right] \right. \\ \left. + \mu_0^2 \sqrt{\Theta} \exp(\bar{u}_{cp}^2) \left[\sqrt{\Theta} (4(\eta_w - 1) + 6\mu_w^2 \eta_w) - \sqrt{2\pi} \mu_w \|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{\text{sl}}\| \text{erf}(\bar{u}_{cp}) \right] \right\}. \quad (4.15)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr}} = -\frac{\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{\text{sl}}}{\|\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{\text{sl}}\|} \begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr,ns}} & \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr,ns}} < \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr,sl}} \\ \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr,sl}} & \text{else} \end{cases}, \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr,ns}} = \left\| \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr}} \cdot \mathbf{n} - (\mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr}} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \cdot \mathbf{n} \right\|, \quad \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr,sl}} = \mu_w \left\| \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr}} \cdot \mathbf{n} \right\| \quad (4.16)$$

The total wall shear stresses:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{fr}} + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{cp}^{\text{kc}} \quad (4.17)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_{\nabla p_f, i} = -V_{dp}[\nabla p_f]_{@i}$ is the pressure gradient force and $\mathbf{F}_{\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f, i} = -V_{dp}[\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau}_f]_{@i}$ denotes the viscous force originated from the deviatoric fluid phase stress tensor, where V_{dp} is the particle volume, and $\mathbf{F}_{drag, i} = \beta_{DEM}([\mathbf{u}_f]_{@i} - \mathbf{u}_{dp, i})$ is the fluid drag force on particle i , where β_{DEM} is the interphase drag coefficient. Here, $[\]_{@i}$ denotes that the fluid phase properties are linearly interpolated to the location of particle i . The Basset force, the virtual mass force, as well as the Saffman and Magnus lift forces are neglected in this paper.

The rotational momentum equation of particle i can be expressed as,

$$I_i \frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{T}_i \quad (4.20)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$ represents the particle rotational velocity and I_i is the particle moment of inertia, which for spherical particles with radius of R_i is equal to $I = \frac{2}{5}m_i R_i^2$. The particle-particle and particle-wall torques, \mathbf{T}_i are calculated as,

$$\mathbf{T}_i = \sum_{i \neq j} R_i \mathbf{n}_{ij} \times \mathbf{F}^t \quad (4.21)$$

The Lagrangian-Eulerian mapping and subsequent smoothing is important in the CFD-DEM simulations of fluid-particle flows. In this paper, we employ the particle centroid method for Lagrangian-Eulerian mapping, where only the particles whose centres lie inside a cell are considered for calculating the mapped Eulerian fields, e.g., discrete particle volume fraction, discrete particle velocity and interphase momentum exchange coefficient for this cell.

It is found that the smoothing of the mapped Eulerian fields is essential to avoid the numerical instabilities, especially in case that particle size is comparable to the computational grid size [37]. Therefore, after obtaining the mapped Eulerian fields, ϕ , a Laplace box filter is employed to smooth these fields,

$$\tilde{\phi}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{1}{7} \left(\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) + \sum_{i=1}^3 (\phi(\mathbf{x} + \Delta_f \mathbf{e}_i, t) + \phi(\mathbf{x} - \Delta_f \mathbf{e}_i, t)) \right) \quad (4.22)$$

where \mathbf{e}_i is the unit vector in i -th direction and Δ_f is the filter size which is equal to the computational grid size. In this work, we smooth discrete particle volume fraction, α_{dp} , discrete particle phase velocity field, \mathbf{u}_{dp} , and interphase drag force, $\mathbf{F}_{drag} = \sum_i^{n_j} w_{ij} \mathbf{F}_{drag, i} V_{dp, i}$, where $\mathbf{F}_{drag, i}$ is the drag force acting on particle i , n_j , number of particles in the cell j , and w_{ij} is the particle weighting function. The particle weighting function quantifies the influence of particle i on cell j . Note that w_{ij} is computed using the particle centroid method, which is 1 if the center of particle i is within cell j and 0 otherwise. It is noteworthy to mention that for smoothing \mathbf{u}_{dp} field, the \mathbf{u}_{dp} field of the surrounding cells is weighted by their corresponding α_{dp} field and at the end of smoothing operation, the obtained field is divided by α_{dp} of the corresponding cell.

TABLE 4.2: Particle contact forces [36].

Normal contact force exerted on particles:

$$\mathbf{F}^n = k_n \boldsymbol{\delta}_{n,ij} - \gamma_n \dot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_{n,ij}$$

Tangential contact force exerted on particles:

$$\mathbf{F}^t = \begin{cases} k_t \boldsymbol{\delta}_{t,ij} - \gamma_t \dot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_{t,ij} & |\mathbf{F}^t| < \mu_{dp} |\mathbf{F}^n| \\ -\mathbf{t} \mu_{dp} |\mathbf{F}^n| & |\mathbf{F}^t| \geq \mu_{dp} |\mathbf{F}^n| \end{cases}$$

Particle normal stiffness coefficient:

$$k_n = \frac{4}{3} E^* \sqrt{R^* \boldsymbol{\delta}_{n,ij}}$$

Particle normal damping coefficient:

$$\gamma_n = -\beta \sqrt{5m^* k_n}, \quad \beta = \frac{\ln(e)}{\sqrt{\ln^2(e) + \pi^2}}$$

Particle tangential stiffness coefficient:

$$k_t = 8G^* \sqrt{R^* \boldsymbol{\delta}_{n,ij}}$$

Particle tangential damping coefficient:

$$\gamma_t = -\beta \sqrt{\frac{10}{3} m^* k_t}$$

Normal unit vector along the line of centers of particle i and j :

$$\mathbf{n}_{ij} \equiv \frac{\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|}$$

Tangential unit vector along the line of centers of particle i and j :

$$\mathbf{t} \equiv \frac{\mathbf{u}_{rt}}{|\mathbf{u}_{rt}|}$$

Effective Young's modulus:

$$E^* = \left(\frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i} + \frac{1 - \nu_j^2}{E_j} \right)^{-1}$$

Effective shear modulus:

$$G^* = \left(\frac{2 - \nu_i}{G_i} + \frac{2 - \nu_j}{G_j} \right)^{-1}$$

Effective particle radius:

$$R^* = \left(\frac{1}{R_i} + \frac{1}{R_j} \right)^{-1}$$

Effective particle mass:

$$m^* = \left(\frac{1}{m_i} + \frac{1}{m_j} \right)^{-1}$$

The reason is to have a weighted contribution of neighbouring cells. This can be important in case of having a significant gradient of α_{dp} field between neighbouring cells.

4.2.3 Interphase momentum exchange coefficient

In fluid-particle flows where the particle-to-fluid density ratio is significantly greater than one, the drag force becomes the dominant source of the interphase momentum exchange. The drag force is characterized by the particle size, the particle shape, the fluid viscosity and density, and the relative velocity between the fluid and particle. In this paper, the drag force models of Beetstra et. al [38] and Tang et al. [39], listed in Table 4.3, are used to perform the simulations. The Reynolds number is $Re = \frac{\alpha_f \rho_f d_s \|\mathbf{u}_f - \mathbf{u}_{cp}\|}{\mu_f}$. Note that in case of the CFD-DEM simulations the Reynolds number is evaluated based on the linearly interpolated fluid phase velocity to the location of the particle, $[\mathbf{u}_f]_{@i}$, and the discrete particle velocity, $\mathbf{u}_{dp,i}$. In addition, the interphase drag coefficient in the CFD-DEM simulations is $\beta_{DEM} = \beta_{TFM} \pi d_{dp}^3 / 6 [\tilde{\alpha}_{dp}]_{@i}$. It is obvious that to compute interphase drag coefficient in the CFD-DEM model, the discrete particle volume fraction, $\tilde{\alpha}_{dp}$, should be evaluated at the location of the particle using the linear interpolation.

TABLE 4.3: Interphase drag coefficient correlations for the TFM simulations

Correlation	Interphase drag coefficient	Re	α_{cp}
Beetstra et al. [38]	$\beta_{TFM} = 180 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_{cp}^2}{d_{cp}^2 \alpha_f} + 18 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_f^3 \alpha_{cp} (1 + 1.5\sqrt{\alpha_{cp}})}{d_{cp}^2}$ $+ 0.31 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_{cp} Re [\alpha_f^{-1} + 3\alpha_f \alpha_{cp} + 8.4 Re^{-0.343}]}{d_{cp}^2 \alpha_f [1 + 10^{3\alpha_{cp}} Re^{-0.5-2\alpha_{cp}}]}$	$20 < Re < 1000$	up to 0.6
Tang et al. [39]	$\beta_{TFM} = 180 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_{cp}^2}{d_{cp}^2 \alpha_f} + 18 \frac{\mu_f \alpha_f^3 \alpha_{cp} (1 + 1.5\sqrt{\alpha_{cp}})}{d_{cp}^2} + \frac{18 \mu_f \alpha_{cp} \alpha_f Re}{d_{cp}^2}$ $\left[0.11 \alpha_{cp} (1 + \alpha_{cp}) - \frac{0.00456}{\alpha_f^4} + \left(0.169 \alpha_f + \frac{0.0644}{\alpha_f^4} \right) Re^{-0.343} \right]$	$Re \leq 1000$	up to 0.6

4.2.4 Hybrid multiscale modelling approach

Concurrently coupling the TFM with the CFD-DEM allows to leverage the benefits of both approaches and achieve an optimal balance between speed-up and accuracy. Therefore, for the first time, we introduce a hybrid model based on the domain decomposition framework, wherein, the TFM simulation governs the embedded CFD-DEM simulation since it covers whole computational domain. Unlike the other hybrid model based on the domain decomposition framework available in the literature [22], [28]–[30], in our hybrid model, the CFD-DEM lives on top of the TFM. In other words, the CFD-DEM acts like a magnification lens and magnifies the continuum particle phase of the TFM simulation with the discrete particles in a specific region

of interest. We will name this region as the discrete magnification lens region throughout this study. The fluid phase is shared between the models in such a way that the fluid phase is solved in the TFM side but takes into account the presence of the discrete particles in the CFD-DEM domain which will be discussed further below in details. we refer to our developed hybrid model as the "discrete magnification lens" model, but for brevity throughout this paper, we will use the abbreviated version of it "DML" model.

The schematic of the DML model is illustrated in Fig. 4.1. The region indicated with the cyan color representing a TFM simulation and the region wrapped inside the overlapping boundary marked by the green color is the CFD-DEM domain. It should be noted that although Fig. 4.1 represents the schematic of the DML model in two-dimensional but the TFM and the CFD-DEM domains are three-dimensional regions. It is obvious that in order to drive a CFD-DEM simulation on top of a TFM one, certain information from the TFM should be transferred to the CFD-DEM. Note that at the magnification lens region, the TFM and the CFD-DEM simulations use the same computational grid. The roles of different sections of the schematic illustrated in Fig. 4.1 are explained in the following,

Overlapping boundary depicted with the green color is the shared border between the TFM and the CFD-DEM domains. It consists of the outer surface of the initial layer of the computational grid cells in the CFD-DEM domain. This boundary is used to measure the entering mass flux of the continuum particle phase to the CFD-DEM on each cell face. Using the measured mass flux of the continuum particle phase at the cell faces, the number of discrete particles to be inserted into the CFD-DEM domain can be calculated by,

$$n_{dp,f} = (\mathbf{S}_f \cdot (\alpha_{cp}\rho_{cp}\mathbf{u}_{cp}))_f \Delta t_{coupling} / m_i \quad (4.23)$$

where, $n_{dp,f}$ is the number of discrete particles to be inserted from the cell face f , $\mathbf{S}_f \cdot (\alpha_{cp}\rho_{cp}\mathbf{u}_{cp})_f$ is the mass flux on the cell face f , which is calculated based on the discretization of the advection term in Eq. (4.3) using the finite volume method, \mathbf{S}_f is the cell face normal vector, and m_i represents the mass of particle i . The coupling time step between the TFM and the CFD-DEM simulations in the DML model is $\Delta t_{coupling}$, which is equal to the TFM time step and the CFD time step of the CFD-DEM model. Note that $n_{p,f}$ is always rounded towards the least integer number, since it is not feasible to insert particle in decimal numbers. In each coupling time step, the residues remaining from the rounding operator for each cell face f are stored and added to the corresponding face mass flux in the subsequent coupling time step.

Insertion region shown with the blue color, represents the region where the discrete particles are inserted. As represented, this region is made up of the first layer of cells near to the overlapping boundary, with each cell belonging to a different boundary face. Consequently, the particles to be inserted based on Equation (4.23) from each cell face f are inserted into their respective cells. Upon insertion of new discrete particles, it is necessary to assign an initial velocity vector

value to them. This initial velocity vector can be obtained by randomly sampling from the Maxwellian velocity distribution. This is because in the derivation of Eq. (4.5) based on the kinetic theory of granular flows, the Chapman-Enskog equations are solved under the assumption of the Maxwellian particle velocity distribution. Hence, the initial values of discrete particle velocity vector can be obtained from,

$$f(\mathbf{u}_{dp,i} - \mathbf{u}_{cp}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\Theta)^{3/2}} e^{\left[-\frac{(\mathbf{u}_{dp,i} - \mathbf{u}_{cp})^2}{2\Theta}\right]} \quad (4.24)$$

where Θ and \mathbf{u}_{cp} are the granular temperature calculated from Eq. (4.5) and the continuum particle phase velocity obtained from solving Eq. (4.3) in the underlying TFM simulation, respectively. These variables are unique to the cell into which the particle will be inserted. Finally, $\mathbf{u}_{dp,i}$ is the sampled velocity vector to be assigned as the initial value of the discrete particle velocity.

Controller region is represented with the red color. In the controller region, the velocity of discrete particles is adjusted to minimize deviation from the continuum particle phase velocity in the cell corresponding to the particle's position. The continuum particle phase velocity is obtained from the underlying TFM simulations by solving Eq. (4.3). It should be noted that the controller region should include the insertion region, and can span up to multiple layers. Because newly inserted particles may be inserted too close to already existing particles in the cell, jittering of the particles may occur; thus, the insertion and controller regions are considered overlapping. The velocity of discrete particles is controlled by applying a force on each particle which is defined as,

$$\mathbf{F}_{controller,i} = \rho_{dp} V_{dp} ([\mathbf{u}_{cp}]_{@i} - \mathbf{u}_{dp,i}) / \Delta t_{coupling} \quad (4.25)$$

It is clear that this force is proportional to the relative velocity between the discrete and the continuum particle phase velocities. It should be noted that the continuum particle phase velocity is interpolated to the position of the discrete particle. This controlling force is also applied to every particle whose center is within the controller region.

Relaxation region is marked with the purple color. To alleviate the possible disturbances on the discrete particles caused by the imposed forces on the particles, such as fluid-particle interaction forces and controller forces, at least a layer of cells is considered as the relaxation region. In this region, the discrete particles are only subjected to the fluid-particle interaction and particle-particle and particle-wall contact forces as outlined in Eq. (4.18), with no additional forces acting upon them.

Two-way coupling region presented with the orange color. So far, the information provided from the underlying TFM simulation has driven the CFD-DEM simulation in an one-way coupled manner; in this region, the discrete particles' information is used to influence the underlying

TFM simulation, resulting in a two-way coupling between the TFM and the CFD-DEM models. Note that this coupling concept is different than the fluid-particle coupling concepts in which the interactions between the particle and the fluid phases determines type of the coupling (e.g., four-way coupling). To accomplish the two-way coupling using the DML model, we introduce two methodologies for various applications,

1. Mass and momentum coupling, can be used when the TFM approach is predicting a completely unphysical behavior. We will refer to this methodology as "DML (mmc)" throughout this paper.
2. Momentum coupling, is used in the cases that although the TFM approach behavior is physical but there is still room for more improvement of the predictions. This method will be referred to "DML (mc)" in this paper.

In the DML (mmc) model, to consider the presence of discrete particles in the continuum phase, the information from the CFD-DEM model affects the continuum particle phase mass equation (Eq. (4.1)), the continuum particle phase velocity (Eq. (4.3)) and the interphase momentum exchange term in the continuum particle phase and fluid momentum equations (Eq. (4.2)-(4.3)). This methodology can be considered as a highly intrusive approach because of enforcing a semi-implicit source term, Ω_{cp} , to continuum particle phase mass equation (Eq. (4.1)). Therefore, in the two-way coupling region, a semi-implicit source term, Ω_{cp} , is added to the RHS of Eq. (4.1). This source term pushes the continuum particle volume fraction field of the underlying TFM towards the discrete particle volume fraction field calculated from the discrete particles. The Ω_{cp} can be described as,

$$\Omega_{cp} = \rho_{cp}(\tilde{\alpha}_{dp}^n - \alpha_{cp}^{n+1})/\Delta t_{coupling} \quad (4.26)$$

where $\tilde{\alpha}_{dp}^n$ is the explicit discrete particle volume fraction and α_{cp}^{n+1} is the implicit continuum particle phase velocity of the TFM. To take into account the presence of the discrete particles in the continuum particle phase momentum equation (Eq. (4.3)), a semi-implicit source term, Ψ_{cp} , is added to the RHS of Eq. (4.3). This source term enforces the continuum particle phase velocity of the underlying TFM towards the discrete particle velocity field. The Ψ_{cp} is defined as,

$$\Psi_{cp} = \alpha_{cp}\rho_{cp}(\mathbf{u}_{cp}^{n+1} - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}^n)/\Delta t_{coupling} \quad (4.27)$$

where \mathbf{u}_{cp}^{n+1} is the implicit continuum particle phase velocity of the TFM model that Eq. (4.3) is solved for it. Also, $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}^n$ is the explicit discrete particle velocity obtained from the CFD-DEM model in the previous time step, n . In addition, in the two-way coupling region, the interphase momentum exchange coefficient of the continuum particle phase and fluid phases, β_{TFM} , as

depicted in Eq. (4.2)-(4.3), is replaced by the interphase momentum exchange coefficient obtained from the CFD-DEM simulations, K^{f-dp} . The interphase momentum exchange coefficient in the CFD-DEM model is computed based on the interphase drag forces of the particles, $\mathbf{F}_{drag,i}$, which are mapped to the computational grid with respect to the particle weighting function, w_{ij} and then smoothed. The K^{f-dp} can be expressed as [40],

$$K^{f-dp} = \frac{1}{V_j} \frac{\|\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{drag}\|}{\|\mathbf{u}_f - \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}\|} \quad (4.28)$$

where the interphase drag force field is $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{drag}$, and V_j is the volume of cell j .

In the DML (mc), we eliminate the semi-implicit source term, Ω_{cp} , from the RHS of Eq. (4.1) and we only consider the effect of the discrete particles on the continuum particle phase momentum equation (Eq. (4.3)) using the same procedure explained in the DML (mmc) model section.

FIGURE 4.1: The schematic of the DML model. The cyan is the TFM simulation domain.

4.3 Numerical Implementation

4.3.1 Solution procedure

The TFM simulations are performed in OpenFOAM using a modified version of *twoPhaseEulerFoam* named *twoPhaseEulerTurbFoam* (<https://github.com/ParticulateFlow/pfmFOAM-public>). We employ a four-way coupling CFD-DEM framework in which fluid–particle, particle–fluid interaction, particle–particle, and particle–wall interactions are considered. In the CFD-DEM simulations, OpenFOAM solves the fluid phase equations on an Eulerian grid while the particles are tracked individually using LIGGGHTS in a Lagrangian framework. The coupling between

the discrete particle and fluid phases is achieved through CFDEMcoupling [41]. In OpenFOAM, the finite volume method is used for spatial discretization, where a collocated grid is applied. In a collocated grid, all variables are calculated and stored at the center of the grid cells. The use of a collocated grid causes the pressure-velocity decoupling problem, which is handled in OpenFOAM using the Rhie-Chow correction [42]. The PIMPLE algorithm which is the combination of Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equations (SIMPLE) method and Pressure Implicit with Splitting of Operators (PISO) method was utilized for the pressure-velocity coupling of the Navier-Stokes equations. In this work, the numerical methods have been implemented in parallel using message passing interface (MPI).

4.3.2 The discrete magnification lens model implementation

This section summarizes the solution procedure used in our DML code. Fig. 4.2 illustrates the schematic of the DML model in one time step. It can be deduced that the time step of TFM, Δt_{TFM} , is equal to the CFD time step of CFD-DEM, Δt_{CFD} , which is the coupling time step between TFM and CFD-DEM, $\Delta t_{coupling}$. As shown, the DML model consists of four consecutive parts: (1) the TFM simulation, (2) the transfer of information from the TFM to the CFD-DEM, (3) the CFD-DEM simulation, and (4) transfer of information from the CFD-DEM to the TFM. Consequently, the solution procedure is divided into four sections with sub-steps and presented here,

1. The TFM model
 - (a) Specify the initial and boundary conditions
 - (b) Solve the continuum particle phase mass equation with semi-implicit source term, Ω_{cp} , (Eq. 4.26) in case of DML (mmc) model or without it in case of DML (mc) model using Multidimensional Universal Limiter with Explicit Solution (MULES [43]) method to obtain α_{cp} (Eq. (4.1))
 - (c) Compute $\alpha_f = 1.0 - \alpha_{cp}$
 - (d) Discretize and linearize the momentum equations (Eq. (4.2)-(4.3))
 - (e) Solve the pressure equation using PIMPLE [44] algorithm
 - (f) Obtain \mathbf{u}_f , \mathbf{u}_{cp} , and p_f fields
2. The TFM to the CFD-DEM information transfer
 - (a) Specify the CFD-DEM region boundaries
 - (b) Measure the entering mass flux of the continuum particle phase through faces of the CFD-DEM region boundaries
 - (c) Select the values of Θ and \mathbf{u}_{cp} in the adjacent cells to the CFD-DEM region boundaries

- (d) Transfer $\mathbf{S}_f \cdot (\alpha_{cp} \rho_{cp} \mathbf{u}_{cp})_f$ to LIGGGHTS and CFDEMcoupling

3. The CFD-DEM

- (a) Insert the discrete particles based on Eq. (4.23) and assign the initial velocity value using a random value from the Maxwellian distribution (Eq. (4.24))
- (b) Compute forces acting on the particle (Eq. (4.18)) and if the particle center is in the controller region apply an additional force to it (Eq. (4.25))
- (c) Update position, velocity, and angular velocity of the particles with the time integration of Eq. (4.18) and (4.20) with Verlet scheme in the DEM time steps
- (d) Localize particles on the Eulerian grid
- (e) Compute the filtered discrete particle phase volume fraction (α_{dp}) from particles with the particle centroid method
- (f) Calculate the filtered discrete particle phase velocity (\mathbf{u}_{dp}) based on the particle weighting function determined by the particle centroid method
- (g) Smoothen α_{dp} and \mathbf{u}_{dp} fields (Eq. (4.22))
- (h) Compute the fluid-particle forces (Eq. (4.19)) to be used in the next DEM time steps using the fluid phase fields obtained from the TFM (e.g., \mathbf{u}_f and p_f)
- (i) Evaluate the controller force (Eq. (4.25)) on the particles in the controller region
- (j) Map the computed interphase drag forces of the particles to the Eulerian grid and smooth it to obtain, $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}_{drag}$ field. Then, calculate the filtered interphase momentum exchange coefficient, K^{f-dp} (Eq. (4.28))
- (k) Smoothen K^{f-dp} field (Eq. (4.22))

4. The CFD-DEM to the TFM information transfer

- (a) Specify the two-way coupling region
- (b) Transfer the filtered and smoothed particle phase velocity field, $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}$, and the filtered interphase momentum exchange coefficient field, K^{f-dp} to the TFM
- (c) Use $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{dp}$ field in the semi-implicit source term, Ψ_{cp} (Eq. (4.27))
- (d) Replace the interphase momentum exchange coefficient in the momentum equations of the TFM, β_{TFM} , with K^{f-dp} field in the two-way coupling region

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Particle jets

A highly effective test case for examining the constraints of the TFM models derived with Chapman-Enskog expansion is the particle-trajectory test [45]–[47], in which two streams of

FIGURE 4.2: The schematic of the discrete magnification lens model implementation in one time step

particles are introduced into a channel and their interaction is determined by their respective particle volume fractions. For instance, in reality, dilute particle jets should cross with a slight interaction, moderate particle jets should scatter due to increased interaction, and the dense one should merge and then scatter. This behavior can be easily captured using Euler-Lagrange models, since momentum of each particle is altered only if a particle-particle collision happens. However, in the TFM, opposite momentum fluxes entering the impingement point are averaged into a single local particle momentum value, resulting in an unphysical merging of the particle jets.

We investigate the performance of the CFD-DEM, the TFM, and the DML models in case of dilute, moderate and dense particle jets. It needs to be mentioned that the predictions of the CFD-DEM simulations are used as the ground truth for numerical validation of the TFM and the DML models. In the simulations, two diagonal jets with velocity of 14 m.s^{-1} were injected from the opposite sides of a channel. The schematic of the geometry of the channel is presented in Fig. 4.3. The fluid flow with velocity of 25 m.s^{-1} entered into the channel from the bottom section and left from the top outlet. In all simulations, at the inlet of the channel, uniform fluid velocity was specified and atmospheric pressure was used at the top of outlet. Moreover, no-slip boundary condition was applied to the fluid phase velocity at the walls. The simulations were performed without including gravitational force and with the drag force model of Beetstra et al. [38]. The grid discretization size was $30 \times 1 \times 60$ ($n_x \times n_y \times n_z$) in all simulations which is equal to $1.5d_p$. The simulation parameters and material properties are listed in Table 4.4. The Δt_{TFM} and Δt_{CFD} were chosen in a way to keep the the maximum courant number well below 1.0. Also, Δt_{DEM} was small enough to prevent large and unphysical overlaps between contacting particles. All simulations presented in this section were performed using second order spatial accuracy for both diffusion (`Gauss linear` [44]) and advection (`SuperBee` [44]) terms in the Navier–Stokes equations. Time advancement is accomplished using the second order accurate `backward` scheme [44]. It needs to be mentioned that in the DML simulations, the two-way coupling between the TFM and the CFD-DEM happens from the initial time of the simulation.

FIGURE 4.3: The schematic of the particle jets channel

TABLE 4.4: Material properties and simulation parameters for particle jets simulations

Property	value	Unit
d_p	2	mm
μ_f	1.8×10^{-5}	$\text{kg.m}^{-1}.\text{s}^{-1}$
ρ_f	1.3	kg.m^{-3}
ρ_s	1000	kg.m^{-3}
e_{p-p}	0.8	-
e_{p-w}	0.95	-
μ_{p-p}	0.05	-
μ_{p-w}	0.05	-
ν (CFD-DEM)	0.3	-
E (CFD-DEM)	5.0×10^7	$\text{kg.m}^{-1}.\text{s}^{-2}$
Δt_{TFM}	5.0×10^{-6}	s
Δt_{CFD}	5.0×10^{-6}	s
Δt_{DEM}	1.0×10^{-7}	s
$\Delta t_{coupling}$	5.0×10^{-6}	s
Simulation time	2	s

4.4.1.1 Dilute particle jets

The time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles of the jets with volume fraction of 0.02 are presented in Fig. 4.4. It is evident that in the CFD-DEM, particle jets are crossing with small extent of interaction, whereas this is not observed in the TFM. This is attributed to the formulation of the TFM approach that lacks the bi-modal velocity distribution which as mentioned earlier it leads to a single local particle velocity value. The particle volume fraction profiles of the DML models illustrate that applying these models on top of a region of the TFM approach can correct the behavior of the TFM simulation. It is obvious that in the DML simulations similar to the CFD-DEM one, the jets cross each other without merging into one dense jet.

The two-way coupling region of DML is shown with red color lines in Fig. 4.4. It needs to be mentioned since we are interested in studying the jet crossing region, discrete magnification lens region was selected in a way to cover the area where the jets interact. Therefore, similar to the TFM, the DML simulations are showing a wrong behavior in the vicinity of the walls. Moreover,

the location of the overlapping boundary, insertion, controller, relaxation and two-way coupling regions are illustrated in Fig. 4.5a. The overlapping boundary is located at $z = 0.024$ m and one cell layer on top of it is the insertion region ($z = 0.024 - 0.027$ m). The controller region including three cell layers, spans from $z = 0.024$ m to $z = 0.033$ m and the two cell layers of relaxation region cover from $z = 0.033$ m to $z = 0.039$ m. The two-way coupling region comprises from thirteen cell layers, starting from $z = 0.039$ m to $z = 0.078$ m. The instantaneous snapshot of the DML simulation can be seen in Fig. 4.5b, which indicates the discrete particles on top the particle volume fraction field of the TFM.

FIGURE 4.4: Time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles in dilute particle jets obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, the DML (mc), and the DML (mmc).

FIGURE 4.5: (a) Schematic of the discrete magnification lens region, (b) Instantaneous snapshot of the DML simulation with discrete particles.

In order to investigate the obtained results in a quantitative manner, the time-averaged particle volume fraction obtained from the simulations are represented in Fig. 4.6. Fig. 4.6a includes the time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles at the location of overlapping boundary ($z = 0.024$ m). Two distinct particle jets are visible in the plots, and the results of the TFM and the DML simulations are coinciding, due to adopting the same TFM simulation set-up in these models. Moreover, the profiles of the TFM and the DML simulations indicate more diffusive particle volume fraction field compared to the CFD-DEM one. This is attributed to the higher numerical diffusion degree of TFM simulations [46]. Measuring particle volume fraction at $z = 0.09$ m (outside the magnification region), indicates that the TFM simulation is behaving

TABLE 4.5: The relative RMSE values of the TFM and the DML models against CFD-DEM over a range of particle volume fractions

Volume fraction	$z = 0.09$ m			$x = 0.045$ m		
	TFM	DML (mc)	DML (mmc)	TFM	DML (mc)	DML (mmc)
0.02	1.7882	0.1811	0.2113	2.8453	0.3277	0.3078
0.05	0.5953	0.3191	0.2348	0.8380	0.2751	0.1925
0.15	0.1241	-	-	0.1029	-	-

completely wrong, while the CFD-DEM and the DML simulations predict particle jet crossing. To assess the results in a quantitative manner, we calculate the relative root mean square error (RMSE) using,

$$relative\ RMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\alpha_{cp,i} - \alpha_{dp,i})^2}{N}}}{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_{dp,i}}{N}} \quad (4.29)$$

where N is the number of data points, $\alpha_{cp,i}$ is the continuum particle volume fraction from the TFM and the DML simulations, and $\alpha_{dp,i}$ is the discrete particle volume fraction from the CFD-DEM simulations.

Evaluating the relative RMSE values of the TFM and the DML simulations against the CFD-DEM data (Table 4.5) reveals that the DML methods significantly reduce the large relative error of the TFM (1.7882) to below 0.22 at $z = 0.09$ m. The particle volume fraction profiles along the channel height at $x = 0.045$ m are depicted in Fig. 4.6c. Although all simulations are predicting a similar trend, but the highest discrepancy compared to the CFD-DEM results belongs to the TFM (see Table 4.5). Also, an increase in the particle volume fraction of the CFD-DEM simulation happens at the end of the channel. This is due to the reflection of the jets from the channel walls which does not exist in the other simulations. Both DML simulations are in a good agreement with the CFD-DEM predictions and have decreased the relative TFM error from 2.8453 to below 0.33 as listed in Table 4.5. It needs to be mentioned that part of the relative error of DML methods is related to the fact that in the CFD-DEM data the reflection of the particle jets from the side walls. This leads to increase of the particle volume fraction in the downstream of the impingement point in the CFD-DEM, while this does not happen in the DML simulations, because we have placed the DML region only in the surrounding of the impingement point. As expected, the particle volume fraction of discrete particles matches well with the one from underlying TFM simulation in the DML (mmc) simulation. However, the particle volume fraction of discrete particles in the DML (mc), does not fit with the one of underlying TFM in the jets intersection region. This is due to excluding the semi-implicit mass source term in Eq. (4.1) in this simulation.

FIGURE 4.6: Comparison of the time-averaged particle volume fraction obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, DML (mc) methodology, and DML (mmc) methodology in dilute particle jets. (a) $z = 0.024$ m, (b) $z = 0.09$ m, and (c) $x = 0.045$ m. It needs to be mentioned that in (c), the dotted lines are representing the discrete particle volume fraction from CFD-DEM part of the DML simulations.

4.4.1.2 Moderate particle jets

As we keep the fluid and particle jet velocities constant and increase the particle volume fraction to 0.05, the particle flow pattern changes as illustrated in Fig. 4.7. Increasing the particle volume fraction, results in more particle collisions in the jets impingement point, leading to scattering of the particles in the rest of the domain. This behavior is visible in all simulations, however in the TFM simulation, a high concentration of particles can be seen in the impingement region. This is due to the lack of bi-modal velocity distribution in the TFM which leads to merging of the jets to some degree. However, this problem does not exist in the profiles of DML simulations, implying that this model is capable of correcting the unphysical behavior of TFM.

To justify our argument about effectiveness of the DML simulations, we further study the particle volume fraction profiles in different heights as displayed in Fig. 4.8. Diffusive particle volume fraction in the jets can be observed from the TFM and the DML simulations at $z = 0.024$ m (Fig. 4.8a) similar to the dilute particle jets. As discussed in Fig. 4.7, some degree of merging of the jets happens in the TFM, which is obvious in Fig. 4.8b, however, the DML models are in better agreement with the CFD-DEM simulations. A comparison between the relative RMSE values between the DML models and CFD-DEM at $z = 0.09$ m reveals that the DML (mmc) is showing superior accuracy than the DML (mc) (refer to Table 4.5). The DML (mmc) and the DML (mc) decrease the relative error of the TFM from 0.5954 to 0.2348 and 0.3191, respectively. The trend of particle volume fraction profiles along the channel height (Fig. 4.8c) is similar between the simulations. However, the particle volume fraction in the impingement region is too large in the TFM simulations. The distribution of particle volume fraction in the CFD-DEM is narrower than the DML models. It needs to be considered that the DML (mmc) and the DML (mc) simulations reduce the relative error of the TFM (0.8380) to 0.1925 and 0.2751, respectively. Also, the particle volume fraction of discrete particles is completely aligning with the values from

underlying TFM in case of using the DML (mmc) method. Nevertheless, this is not happening in case of the DML (mc) method.

FIGURE 4.7: Time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles in moderate particle jets calculated from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, the DML (mc) methodology, and DML (mmc) methodology.

FIGURE 4.8: Comparison of the time-averaged particle volume fraction obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM, DML (mc) methodology, and DML (mmc) methodology in moderate particle jets. (a) $z = 0.024$ m, (b) $z = 0.09$ m, and (c) $x = 0.045$ m. It needs to be mentioned in (c), the dotted lines are representing the discrete particle volume fraction from the CFD-DEM part of the DML simulations.

4.4.1.3 Dense particle jets

By increasing the particle volume fraction of particle jets to 0.15, one should expect more particle collisions and energy loss, leading to merging of the jets into one dense jet as demonstrated in Fig. 4.9. However, downstream of the impingement point, particle collisions cause scattering particles away from the center of the channel. It is clear that in dense particle flows, TFM behaves similar to the CFD-DEM, implying the applicability of the TFM in dense particle-laden flows. Since the results of the TFM are in a good agreement with the CFD-DEM, then there is no need to apply DML models here. This also can be interpreted from Fig. 4.10, where the particle volume fraction profiles correspond well to the ones from the CFD-DEM at $z = 0.024$ m, $z = 0.09$ m, and $x = 0.045$ m. Also, the relative RMSE values in Table 4.5 for dense particle jets, confirm the well correspondence of the TFM results to the CFD-DEM ones.

FIGURE 4.9: Time-averaged particle volume fraction profiles in dense particle jets obtained from the CFD-DEM and the TFM.

FIGURE 4.10: Comparison of the time-averaged particle volume fraction obtained from the CFD-DEM and the TFM in dense particle jets. (a) $z = 0.024$ m, (b) $z = 0.09$ m, and (c) $x = 0.045$ m.

4.4.2 Unbounded fluidization

Unbounded fluidization (also known as sedimentation) is adopted to replicate clusters of the particles in fluid-particle systems and is distinguished by a relative velocity between the particle and the fluid phases. The clusters are defined as persistent, transient and heterogeneous structures of particles and extensively impact mass, momentum and energy transport in the system [48]. These clusters and streamers of particles form because of (i) inertia between the particle phase, gravity and particle-fluid drag and (ii) dissipation of fluctuating energy of particles due to inelastic collisions and viscous damping [49]. Usually, in unbounded fluidization simulations, no forces act in the transverse directions, whereas a constant body force, i.e. gravity, acts in negative z -direction. The fluid pressure is divided into a fluctuating (local) component superimposed by a linear gradient, where the latter opposes gravity and supports the weight of the suspension, i.e. [50],

$$\nabla p_f = (\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d \rho_p + (1 - \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d) \rho_f) \mathbf{g} \quad (4.30)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle_d$ denotes the domain average. This force is added as an additional body force to the particles and the fluid, so that no net acceleration occurs and the system stays statistically steady.

A significant challenge in accurately modelling fluid-particle systems is clustering. It has been shown in the literature that the CFD-DEM and the TFM simulations are capable of capturing the dynamic behavior of the clusters [48], [50], [51]. However, according to findings of Fullmer and Hrenya [48], the domain-averaged slip velocity values of the TFM show relative errors of less than 20% compared to the CFD-DEM results over a range of particle volume fractions. In this section, our aim is to examine the ability of the DML model in reproducing the particle clusters and in improving the TFM predictions. Unlike the previous studies [48], [51] in addition to comparing the domain-averaged slip velocity in the vertical direction, $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$ with the CFD-DEM data, we extend the comparison to the domain-averaged variance of particle volume fraction, $\langle \alpha_p'^2 \rangle_d = \langle \alpha_p \alpha_p \rangle_d - \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$, and turbulent kinetic energy of the particle phase, $\langle \mathbf{k}_s \rangle_d = 1/2(\langle \alpha_p \mathbf{u}_p \cdot \mathbf{u}_p \rangle_d - \langle \alpha_p \mathbf{u}_p \rangle_d \cdot \langle \alpha_p \mathbf{u}_p \rangle_d / \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d)$. It needs to be mentioned that in contrast to the previous studies [48], [51] that have adopted the CFD-DEM results of Radl and Sundaresan [50], we have performed the CFD-DEM simulations with our developed CFD-DEM code.

4.4.2.1 Numerical validation

We verify our CFD-DEM predictions of the unbounded fluidization of Geldart A particle with the ones from Radl and Sundaresan work [50] in a 3D periodic domain with the size of $0.008 \text{ m} \times 0.008 \text{ m} \times 0.032 \text{ m}$. Then, the TFM results are validated against our CFD-DEM simulations. Results of the CFD-DEM simulations are the ideal type of data for numerical validation of the TFM, since like the TFM, in the CFD-DEM, the flow around the particle phase is not resolved and this allows to apply the same drag force closure in both approaches. This numerical validation of the TFM against CFD-DEM, isolates the validation of the continuum closure (kinetic-collisional solids stress, the frictional solids stress, and so forth).

The material properties and simulation parameters are listed in Table 4.6. Different domain-averaged particle volume fractions varying from 0.05 to 0.20 were simulated using the CFD-DEM and the TFM approaches. The corresponding number of discrete particles related to each domain-averaged particle volume fraction is listed in Table 4.7. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in all three directions. The grid discretization size was chosen based on the Radl and Sundaresan work [50], and was $32 \times 32 \times 128$ ($n_x \times n_y \times n_z$) in all simulations which is equal to $3.33d_p$. Selecting the proper time step for the CFD-DEM and the TFM simulations of unbounded fluidization of Geldart A particles is of utmost importance for the convergence of the solution. All simulations of this section were conducted using second order spatial accuracy for both diffusion (**Gauss linear** [44]) and advection (**SuperBee** [44]) terms in the Navier–Stokes equations. Time advancement is accomplished using the second order accurate **backward** scheme [44]. Also, the relaxation factors in PIMPLE loop for fluid phase velocity and pressure were 0.6

and 0.3. It needs to be mentioned that initially the particle phase is distributed randomly in the system to reduce the required simulation time to reach to the statistical steady state.

Typically, in CFD-DEM simulations time integration of the particle-particle contact equations limits the choice of the time step. The Rayleigh criterion is based on the principle that contact energy cannot propagate beyond the in-contact neighbouring particles in a single time step and reads as [52],

$$t_R = \frac{\pi R \sqrt{\rho_p / G}}{0.1631\nu + 0.8766} \quad (4.31)$$

where t_R is Rayleigh time, and shear modulus, G , is $G = E/2(1 + \nu)$. Typically in DEM simulations, 10 to 20% of Rayleigh time is used as the DEM time step [53]. In our simulations $t_R = 8.14 \cdot 10^{-6}$ s and thus, the Δt_{DEM} is about 12% of t_R . It needs to be considered that in the CFD-DEM simulations, in addition to Rayleigh time criterion, particle relaxation time, τ_p , also needs to be checked. Particle relaxation time, τ_p , or particle response time with assuming Stokes drag law can enforce the upper bound of Δt_{DEM} and is defined as,

$$\tau_p = \frac{d_p^2 \rho_p}{18\mu_f} \quad (4.32)$$

The τ_p can be interpreted as the time necessary to accelerate the particle to a certain fluid velocity via drag force. Therefore, Δt_{DEM} should be smaller than this time. In our simulations, $\tau_p = 0.044$ s, which indicates that the chosen Δt_{DEM} is well below the particle relaxation time.

There are different criteria for determining Δt_{CFD} similar to Δt_{DEM} . One criterion is fluid relaxation time, τ_{fluid} . This time is similar to the particle relaxation time and is an indicator of the time necessary to accelerate fluid to a certain particle velocity via drag force and is,

$$\tau_{fluid} = \frac{d_p^2}{18\mu_f} \frac{1 - \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d}{\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d} \quad (4.33)$$

It can be seen that τ_{fluid} is a function of domain-averaged particle volume fraction in the system. This time imposes the upper bound for the time step of solving Navier-Stokes equations. Thus, the chosen Δt_{CFD} should be smaller than τ_{fluid} . The calculated values of τ_{fluid} for the range of different domain-averaged particle volume fraction used in this paper can be found in Table 4.8. Due to presence of the particles in the system, at the scale of the particle size wakes form behind them, which enhances the fluid turbulence and is called pseudo-turbulence. Although, the fluid turbulence increases the fluid relaxation time, τ_{fluid} , but on the other hand, the presence of more particles in the system, damps the fluid turbulence. Therefore, as is evident in Table 4.8, by increasing the domain-averaged particle volume fraction, the fluid relaxation time decreases. random spatial distribution of the particles and their uncorrelated This can be attributed to the damping of the psuedo-turbulence arising from the random spatial distribution of the particles and their uncorrelated The other criterion is the courant number, that also can impose the

upper bound of Δt_{CFD} . In our simulations using the reported value of Δt_{CFD} in Table 4.6, the maximum courant number was below 1.0.

TABLE 4.6: Material properties and simulation parameters for the unbounded fluidization simulations

Property	value	Unit
d_p	75	μm
μ_f	1.8×10^{-5}	$\text{kg.m}^{-1}.\text{s}^{-1}$
ρ_f	1.3	kg.m^{-3}
ρ_s	1500	kg.m^{-3}
e_{p-p}	0.9	-
μ_{p-p}	0.1	-
ν (CFD-DEM)	0.42	-
E (CFD-DEM)	1.0×10^6	$\text{kg.m}^{-1}.\text{s}^{-2}$
Δt_{TFM}	5.0×10^{-5}	s
Δt_{CFD}	5.0×10^{-5}	s
Δt_{DEM}	1.0×10^{-6}	s
$\Delta t_{coupling}$	5.0×10^{-5}	s

TABLE 4.7: Calculated number of discrete particles with different domain-averaged particle volume fraction in the CFD-DEM simulations.

$\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$	N_{dp}
0.05	463572
0.1	927145
0.15	1390717
0.2	1854289

TABLE 4.8: Calculated values of τ_f with different domain-averaged particle volume fractions

$\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d$	τ_f
0.05	3.3×10^{-4} s
0.1	1.5×10^{-4} s
0.15	9.8×10^{-5} s
0.2	6.9×10^{-5} s

The predicted values of the mean-slip Reynolds numbers, $Re_{slip} = \rho_f d_p \langle u_{slip} \rangle_d / \mu_f$ obtained from the slip velocity in the vertical direction,

$$\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d = \frac{\langle (1 - \alpha_p) u_{fz} \rangle_d}{1 - \langle \alpha_p \rangle_d} - \frac{\langle \alpha_p u_{pz} \rangle_d}{\langle \alpha_p \rangle_d} \quad (4.34)$$

for the CFD-DEM and the TFM simulations are demonstrated in Fig. 4.11. The time-averaging window of the domain-averaged slip velocity in the CFD-DEM simulations of Radl and Sundaresan [50] was $30\tau'_p$, while in our TFM and CFD-DEM simulations, it was considered to be $43\tau'_p$. The particle characteristic time, $\tau'_p = u_t/|\mathbf{g}|$, where the terminal velocity of a single particle is, $u_t = 0.232 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$. It is necessary to note that the averaging process starts when the statistical steady state is established. As can be deduced from Fig. 4.11, our CFD-DEM simulations match well with the results of Radl and Sundaresan [50]. However, there are discrepancies between the data, this can be attributed to the difference in numerical implementations of the CFD-DEM solvers, but overall both CFD-DEM results predict a similar trend. The mean-slip Reynolds number is relatively constant at low domain-averaged particle volume fractions and decreases at higher domain-averaged particle volume fractions. We need to note that, although

flow is in statistical steady state, but the instantaneous domain-averaged slip velocity fluctuates around its mean value, due to breaking and forming of the clusters. Qualitatively, the TFM is in good agreement with our CFD-DEM results and the relative error between our TFM and CFD-DEM simulations for four cases (from the lowest to the highest $\langle\alpha_p\rangle_d$) are: 12.4, 16.41, 15.57 and 14.13 %. The TFM is systematically under-predicting the mean-slip Reynolds number. By-passing of the fluid flow from the dilute and low particle volume fraction region, increases the domain-averaged slip velocity. Therefore, increasing the size and number of the clusters in the system can lead to higher domain-averaged slip velocity and thus higher mean-slip Reynolds number. However, in higher $\langle\alpha_p\rangle_d$ values the clusters reach to the maximum packing limit and this causes to decrease of the domain-averaged slip velocity, as can be seen in Fig. 4.11. The lower values of domain-averaged slip velocity of the TFM in Fig. 4.11 can be related to the lower degree of clustering compared to the CFD-DEM which is evident from lower value of $\overline{\langle\alpha_p^2\rangle}_d$ in the TFM simulation compared to the CFD-DEM (see Table 4.14). This is also partially visible in Fig. 4.12, where the instantaneous particle volume fraction profiles of the CFD-DEM and the TFM at various domain-averaged particle volume fractions are presented. The under-prediction of the mean-slip Reynolds number in the TFM is related to the smaller clusters formed. This can be due to the higher predicted solids pressure values which arises from the fact that particle-particle interactions are resolved using continuum closures rather than physical models (e.g., soft-sphere in the CFD-DEM). In order to address this issue in the TFM, we apply our developed DML (mc) method on the TFM simulations with $\langle\alpha_p\rangle_d = 0.05$. The DML (mc) method will help us to resolve the particle-particle interactions in a small DML region and thus we can examine that if resolving these interactions in a small region of the TFM can improve the TFM predictions in the whole system. It needs to be mentioned that we do not use the DML (mmc) approach in here, because the TFM is capable of capturing the physics of the clustering and we are only interested in improving the TFM results.

4.4.2.2 Dilute unbounded fluidization

In this section, we apply our developed DML (mc) approach in case of unbounded fluidization with $\langle\alpha_p\rangle_d = 0.05$. Fig. 4.13a demonstrates the location of the DML region. We have chosen a DML region in the middle of the simulation domain to investigate the impact of the DML (mc) approach on the TFM simulation. There are two overlapping boundaries, one is in the top at $z = 0.020$ m and the other one is located in the bottom at $z = 0.012$ m. The insertion regions in the top and bottom contain one cell layer, at $z = 0.020 - 0.01975$ m in the top and $z = 0.012 - 0.01225$. In this particular schematic, the controller region comprises of two cell layers, starting from $z = 0.020$ to $z = 0.0195$ in the top section and from $z = 0.012$ to $z = 0.0125$ in the bottom. The relaxation regions are made up two cell layers in the top ($z = 0.0195 - 0.019$ m) and in the bottom ($z = 0.0125 - 0.013$ m). Finally, the two-way coupling region which

FIGURE 4.11: Comparison of mean-slip Reynolds numbers between our CFD-DEM, the TFM, and the CFD-DEM results of Radl and Sundaresan [50] for various domain-averaged particle volume fractions.

FIGURE 4.12: Instantaneous particle volume fraction profiles for various domain-averaged particle volume fractions obtained from the CFD-DEM (top row) and the TFM (bottom row) simulations.

includes twenty four cell layers, stretches from $z = 0.013$ m to $z = 0.019$ m. In these simulations, the two-way coupling between the TFM and the CFD-DEM in the DML region, happens after

the underlying TFM simulation reaches to a statistically steady state. The instantaneous of the DML (mc) approach in Fig. 4.13b, indicates the discrete particles on top of the particle volume fraction field of underlying TFM. The preferential concentration of the discrete particles with the fluid flow which leads to clustering can be seen.

FIGURE 4.13: (a) Schematic of the discrete magnification lens region, (b) Instantaneous snapshot of the DML (mc) simulation with discrete particles.

To quantitatively compare the predictions of the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc), we evaluate the mean and standard deviation values of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$, $\langle \mathbf{k}_s \rangle_d$, and $\langle \overline{\alpha_p'^2} \rangle_d$ in the DML region with a time-averaging window of $43\tau_p'$ and list the results in Table 4.9-4.11.

The results indicate that overall, applying the DML (mc) approach improves the TFM results in the DML region. However, depending on the number of controller cell layers the efficiency of the DML (mc) approach increases. It is clear that in case of having no controller region, the DML (mc) predictions are close to the TFM ones, but with adding one, two and three layers of cells, the relative error between the CFD-DEM and the TFM in case of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$, decreases from 12.47% to 8.58, 7.43 and 10.71%, respectively. Moreover, the relative error of $\langle \mathbf{k}_s \rangle_d$ in the TFM drops from 28.82% to 22.35, 17.06, and 22.94%, respectively. Finally, the relative error of the TFM in case of $\langle \overline{\alpha_p'^2} \rangle_d$, reduces from 43.47% respectively to 30.47, 26.08, and 34.78%. All simulations with at least one controller cell layer are demonstrating better results than the TFM which indicative of the robustness of our developed DML (mc) approach. Also, it can be deduced that in this unbounded fluidization case, the optimal choice of number of controller cell layers is two, which implies the use of two cell layers of relaxation region is necessary to gain the most accurate results.

To examine the impact of the DML (mc) simulations on the properties of the full simulation domain, the comparison between the mean and standard deviation values of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$, $\langle \mathbf{k}_s \rangle_d$, and $\langle \overline{\alpha_p'^2} \rangle_d$ obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) simulations is presented in Table 4.12-4.14.

TABLE 4.9: Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$ in the DML region obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the CFD-DEM value.

Approach	Number of controller cell layers	Mean Val.	St. Dev.	% Rel. Err.
CFD-DEM	-	0.3135	0.0276	-
TFM	-	0.2744	0.0247	12.47
DML (mc)	-	0.2755	0.03884	12.12
DML (mc)	1	0.2866	0.0285	8.58
DML (mc)	2	0.2902	0.0271	7.43
DML (mc)	3	0.2799	0.0270	10.71

TABLE 4.10: Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle \mathbf{k}_s \rangle_d$ in the DML region obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the CFD-DEM value.

Approach	Number of controller cell layers	Mean Val.	St. Dev.	% Rel. Err.
CFD-DEM	-	0.0170	0.0041	-
TFM	-	0.0121	0.0030	28.82
DML (mc)	-	0.0121	0.0028	28.82
DML (mc)	1	0.0132	0.0032	22.35
DML (mc)	2	0.0141	0.0021	17.06
DML (mc)	3	0.0131	0.0026	22.94

TABLE 4.11: Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle \overline{\alpha_p^2} \rangle_d$ in the DML region obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the CFD-DEM value.

Approach	Number of controller cell layers	Mean Val.	St. Dev.	% Rel. Err.
CFD-DEM	-	0.0023	0.0005	-
TFM	-	0.0013	0.0004	43.47
DML (mc)	-	0.0013	0.0005	43.47
DML (mc)	1	0.0016	0.0005	30.47
DML (mc)	2	0.0017	0.0005	26.08
DML (mc)	3	0.0015	0.0004	34.78

It is obvious that similar to the results in the DML region only, the DML (mc) simulation without controller region, produces similar results to the TFM. Nevertheless, increasing the number of controller cell layers, results in correcting the behavior of the TFM. The relative error of the TFM compared to the CFD-DEM data in case of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$, lowers from 12.42% to 7.59, 7.33, and 10.69% using one, two and three controller cell layers, respectively. The same trend happens to the relative error values of $\langle \mathbf{k}_s \rangle_d$, it falls from 25.29% for the TFM, to 15.52, 13.79, and 24.71% in the DML (mc) simulations. At last, the relative error of the TFM in case of $\langle \overline{\alpha_p^2} \rangle_d$, decreases from 39.13% to 26.09, 21.74, and 30.43%, respectively. It is also evident that the DML (mc) simulation with two controller and relaxation cell layers is showing superior accuracy.

TABLE 4.12: Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle u_{slip} \rangle_d$ in the full domain obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the CFD-DEM value.

Approach	Number of controller cell layers	Mean Val.	St. Dev.	% Rel. Err.
CFD-DEM	-	0.3123	0.0193	-
TFM	-	0.2735	0.0164	12.42
DML (mc)	-	0.2740	0.0199	12.26
DML (mc)	1	0.2886	0.0170	7.59
DML (mc)	2	0.2894	0.0126	7.33
DML (mc)	3	0.2789	0.0149	10.69

TABLE 4.13: Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle k_s \rangle_d$ in the full domain obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the CFD-DEM value.

Approach	Number of controller cell layers	Mean Val.	St. Dev.	% Rel. Err.
CFD-DEM	-	0.0174	0.0034	-
TFM	-	0.0130	0.0022	25.29
DML (mc)	-	0.0131	0.0019	24.71
DML (mc)	1	0.0147	0.0029	15.52
DML (mc)	2	0.0150	0.0014	13.79
DML (mc)	3	0.0131	0.0017	24.71

TABLE 4.14: Comparison of mean and standard deviation values of $\langle \alpha_p^2 \rangle_d$ in the full domain obtained from the CFD-DEM, the TFM and the DML (mc) approaches. The relative error is based on the mean values and calculated with regard to the CFD-DEM value.

Approach	Number of controller cell layers	Mean Val.	St. Dev.	% Rel. Err.
CFD-DEM	-	0.0023	0.0002	-
TFM	-	0.0014	0.0001	39.13
DML (mc)	-	0.0014	0.0002	39.13
DML (mc)	1	0.0017	0.0001	26.09
DML (mc)	2	0.0018	0.0001	21.74
DML (mc)	3	0.0016	0.0001	30.43

4.5 Conclusion and outlook

This chapter covered development of a novel, robust and accurate hybrid multiscale modelling approach called "discrete magnification lens". In this method, the CFD-DEM approach lives on top of a region of interest in a TFM simulation. The methodology and numerical implementation of the developed method was explained in details. It was found that the mapping and the following smoothing of the discrete particle data is of utmost importance for the success of the method. In addition, our studies of the particle-trajectory test cases with dilute, moderate and dense particle jets, revealed the effectiveness of the discrete magnification lens method in revising the unphysical behavior of the TFM simulation towards a physical prediction similar to the CFD-DEM. Moreover, applying the discrete magnification lens method to the TFM simulations of a unbounded fluidization case decreased the relative error between the TFM and the CFD-DEM results. Also, it was found that the discrete particle insertion method applied in the discrete magnification lens approach is capable of reproducing the existing particle clusters seen in the underlying TFM approach. Nevertheless, the main advantage of the discrete magnification lens method is that it can effectively correct the unphysical behavior of the TFM in a specific region of interest. Thus, it can be used locally in a TFM simulation to fix the behavior of the TFM approach in that region.

The future studies will focus on applying discrete magnification lens method in the complex fluid-particle systems, such as fluidized beds, spout-fluidized beds and risers and validate the results against experimental data.

4.6 Best Practice Guidelines

This section lists the different best practice guidelines that can be kept in mind during developing hybrid continuum-discrete multiscale methods.

- Developing and implementing the hybrid continuum-discrete multiscale methods is a complex procedure, due to the different treatment of the particle phase in the continuum and discrete methods. First step in developing such models is to decide if the discrete method (CFD-DEM) should live on top of the continuum method (TFM) or it will cover a separated region. In case of having a separated region for the discrete model, one needs to adopt strategies like multi-region solvers in OpenFOAM, which would require extensive development efforts. The significant drawback of this method is that it requires additional computational loops to couple the solution of the regions and thus the computational time would increase compared to a TFM simulation. However, the main advantage is that the fluid phase momentum equation can be solved independently in the magnification lens region. Our experience has shown that developing multi-region solvers for multiphase flows is too complicated and the accurate coupling between the two regions is difficult to reach. As discussed in this chapter, we have chosen to build our hybrid model in a way that discrete method lives on top of the continuum one.
- Mapping (coarse-graining) of the Lagrangian data to a Eulerian field is one of the important steps of the developing hybrid solvers. The two-way coupling between the discrete and continuum methods requires mapping of the properties of the discrete particle phase (volume, velocity) to an Eulerian grid.
- The consecutive smoothing of the obtained Eulerian field from the Lagrangian data has a prominent impact on the efficiency and the stability of the hybrid solver. This is due to dependence of the TFM approach on the particle velocity gradient to calculate the granular temperature and kinetic-collisional particle stress. An inappropriate discrete particle velocity field can lead to the instability of the underlying TFM simulation and therefore, to failure of the simulation.
- Typically the TFM produces reliable and physical results in case of applying it in different fluid-particle systems. However, in some cases with much more complicated geometries and flow patterns, it might be unable to predict physical results in a small portion of the system. This will lead to unphysical and wrong predictions in the whole system. Thus, it is important to determine and choose a region in the system that the TFM is failing in that section to apply the developed hybrid model. This will improve the accuracy of the underlying TFM method and also will be efficient from the point of view of the computational demand.

- Although as we discussed in section 4.4.2, applying the hybrid method may reduce the relative error of the predictions of the TFM compared to the CFD-DEM in case of Unbounded fluidization. Nevertheless, the effectiveness and importance of this method can solely be seen in cases where the TFM, due to its formulation nature, is unable to capture the real world physics e.g., the particle jets (section 4.4.1). In addition, this method can be only applied to a small region of interest in the TFM simulation and it should not be adopted in a large portion of the TFM simulation domain, because it will increase the computational time drastically.

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Chapter 5

Data-based recurrence CFD

5.1 Introduction

Numerical simulations possess the capability to virtually replicate any system within our computer realm, empowering us as omnipotent observers capable of altering the laws of physics and extracting valuable insights to expand our understanding of phenomena or processes [1]. In instances where conducting real experiments proves hazardous, time-intensive, expensive, or simply unfeasible, computer simulations present a practical and accessible alternative. Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) stands as a potent simulation method renowned for its ability to deliver detailed solutions for fluid flow, heat transfer, mass transfer, and other phenomena, both in terms of time and space. Modelling fluid dynamics and chemical engineering processes using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) methods is becoming increasingly common. CFD simulations can offer detailed insights into flow and heat transfer phenomena occurring within reactors, vessels, or equipment, especially in situations where obtaining reliable measurements is either impossible or highly challenging and costly. Apart from the diverse length scales involved, industrial processes also exhibit considerable variations in time scales, spanning from milliseconds (for resolving particle collisions) to minutes and hours (for determining residence times in industrial-scale reactors) ([2]–[4]). Thus, achieving an effective time extrapolation in numerical simulations becomes crucial for transitioning from an industrial plant scale to an industrial process scale [5]. Numerous research groups worldwide are focused on exploring innovative methods to reduce the computational expenses associated with numerical simulations. Among these approaches is Data-based Recurrence CFD simulations, which emerge as an efficient technique for time extrapolation, capable of aligning with real-time dynamics.

5.2 Methodology

Chemical engineering and the process industry need time-extrapolation of the particulate process in numerical simulations since the classical methodologies are too computationally demanding and expensive. Lichtenegger.T and Pirker.S (Eg.[2], [5]) suggested an effective method to time-extrapolate particulate flows, which may meet the demand for quicker simulation strategies in the process industry. This solution addressed the issues of cost and computational capabilities.

5.2.1 Numerical Modelling

5.2.1.1 Equation-based Two-Fluid Model

A popular method in computational fluid dynamics (CFD) for simulating multiphase flows, especially those involving gas-solid or gas-liquid interactions, is the Two-fluid Model (TFM). In the case of the Eulerian-Eulerian TFM approach, both gas and solid are considered interpenetrating continua as described in ([6], [7]). The governing equations are the continuity equations for gas and solid, momentum conservation equations for gas and solid, and energy equations for each phase.

Continuity equations for gas and solid phases:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_g \rho_g}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_g \rho_g \mathbf{u}_g) = 0 \quad (5.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_s \rho_s}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s) = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

Where α is the volume fraction for gas or solid phase, ρ is the density of gas or solid phase, \mathbf{u} is the velocity of gas or solid phase, and t is the time.

Momentum equations for fluid phase and solid phases:

$$\frac{\partial (\alpha_g \rho_g \mathbf{u}_g)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_g \rho_g \mathbf{u}_g \mathbf{u}_g) = -\nabla p_g + \nabla \cdot \tau_g + \alpha_g \rho_g \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{F}_g \quad (5.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s \mathbf{u}_s) = -\nabla p_s + \nabla \cdot \tau_s + \alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{F}_s \quad (5.4)$$

Where p is the pressure on either gas or solid phase, τ represents viscous stresses in gas or solid phase, \mathbf{g} is the gravitational acceleration, and \mathbf{F} represents external forces acting on gas or solid phases.

Energy equations for gas and solid phases:

$$\frac{\partial (\alpha_g \rho_g E_g)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_g \rho_g \mathbf{u}_g E_g) = \nabla \cdot (\lambda_g \nabla T_g) - \nabla \cdot (\alpha_g \rho_g \mathbf{u}_g h_g) + \dot{q}_g + \dot{Q}_{r,g} \quad (5.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\alpha_s \rho_s E_s)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s E_s) = \nabla \cdot (\lambda_s \nabla T_s) - \nabla \cdot (\alpha_s \rho_s \mathbf{u}_s h_s) + \dot{q}_s + \dot{Q}_{r,s} \quad (5.6)$$

Where E is the total energy per unit volume, T is the temperature of gas or solid phase, λ is the thermal conductivity, h is the enthalpy of either gas or solid phase, $\dot{Q}_{r,(g,s)}$ represents any radiative heat transfer term specific to gas or solid phase as described in ([6], [8]).

We maintain TFM simulations as the fundamental reference simulations for lab-scale fluidized beds to compare them with data-based rCFD simulations, which is explained in 5.2.1.2.

5.2.1.2 Data-driven Models: Data-based recurrence CFD (rCFD)

We will refrain from discussing running Two-Fluid Model simulations for the following, and the Work Package 3 report on Application examples provides a thorough explanation of the procedures involved in running data-based rCFD simulations. The fundamental components of data-based rCFD are outlined for readability and comprehension and are followed by the numerical calibration techniques 5.2.2.

In the case of the transport-based rCFD method, a Lagrangian representation of fluid flow is used instead of the Eulerian field representation ([5], [9]). In this instance, the motion of massless tracer particles characterizes the fluid flow. As a result, snapshots of (Lagrangian) tracer motions rather than snapshots of (Eulerian) field values fill the database. The latter becomes discretized form and becomes snapshots of convective cell-to-cell paths [5]. Once more, a flow candidate can be expanded beyond the database's time span by using the same Markov-alike recurrence process, but this time, transport (i.e., cell-to-cell shift) operations are applied instead of rebuilding the flow field itself.

The two main components of the rCFD technique are the generation of the database and the utilization of the database ([4], [10]). The application of the data is predicated on Eulerian field characteristics, recurrence statistics, and Lagrangian cell-to-cell connectivity patterns. The data creation is accomplished using CFD simulation with TFM method. A detailed flow sheet of the process is shown in the figure 5.1.

FIGURE 5.1: Flow-sheet of Data-based recurrence CFD simulation approach.

5.2.2 Numerical Calibration

Numerical calibration of fluidized bed simulations involves adjusting the parameters and settings within the computational model to ensure that the simulated behavior closely matches numerical experiments performed with expensive, high-fidelity simulation methods. This process typically entails fine-tuning various aspects of the simulation, such as particle properties, fluid dynamics parameters, and boundary conditions, to achieve accurate predictions of fluidized bed behavior. By iteratively adjusting the simulation setup and comparing the results to experimental data or theoretical expectations, researchers can validate and refine the numerical model, improving its predictive capabilities for real-world applications.

5.2.2.1 1D calibration by varying face swaps

In lab-scale fluidized bed simulations, adjusting the flux becomes necessary to tackle global diffusion. Flux refers to the movement of substances across a medium, such as the dispersion of particles in a fluid through diffusion. In our study of secondary gas injection and solid mixing, we primarily focused on the global diffusion of species concentration within the domain. The alteration of flux is governed by Fick's law of diffusion for global diffusion balance [11], and is given by,

$$J = -D \frac{dC}{dx} \quad (5.7)$$

where, J represents the flux of the substance (the rate of transfer of particles per unit area per unit time). D is the diffusion coefficient, which quantifies how easily the substance diffuses through the medium. dC/dx represents the concentration gradient of a substance changes over time within a specific region.

A crucial consideration is global diffusion, which involves the movement of substances throughout the entire simulation domain. In our research, we tackle global diffusion by manipulating flux, which quantifies substance transfer. Our focus is on adjusting face swap diffusivity, a parameter in the rCFD framework enabling control over substance diffusion across various interfaces or regions within the simulated system. To achieve unique outcomes distinct from traditional TFM simulations, the data-driven rCFD method requires case-specific calibration. We manage global diffusion by adjusting flux, particularly by varying face swap diffusivity, which is applied across the entire domain. By varying face swap diffusivity, we can effectively modulate the rate and extent of diffusion processes throughout the domain. This means we can influence how particles disperse and interact within the simulated environment, leading to more accurate representations of real-world phenomena. In essence, by managing global diffusion through the adjustment of flux and face swap diffusivity, the data-driven rCFD method can provide distinct and tailored results that have very good agreements with classical TFM simulation methods.

5.2.2.2 3D calibration by Checkerboarding

Here, we aim to introduce the Checkerboarding technique for analyzing and visualizing flow patterns within computational domains in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations. It serves as a valuable tool for researchers across various fields, aiding in the comprehension of intricate flow patterns and concentration distributions within fluidized bed systems. Rendering a checkerboard pattern in fluidized beds involves visually representing the distribution of different fluidization conditions or properties within the bed.

Here, we will use checkerboarding specifically to investigate local diffusion [12] occurring within the lab-scale fluidized domain. When addressing local diffusion, we rely on Fick's second law [11], which explains how the concentration of a substance changes over time within a specific region and is given by,

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \quad (5.8)$$

where, $\frac{\partial C}{\partial t}$ represents the rate of change of concentration concerning time. $\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2}$ is the second derivative of concentration concerning distance, indicating how concentration changes spatially within the medium.

Specifically, checkerboarding is employed to model the fluidized bed domain, facilitating the study of objectives such as gas-solid mixing, convection, diffusion processes, and heat or mass transfer within both the gas and solid phases. This technique typically involves assigning different concentration levels distinct colors, often red and blue, to create a checkerboard pattern that aids in distinguishing between various flow regimes.

In our implementation, we utilized Ansys/Fluent User Defined Functions (UDFs) ([13], [14]) to implement checkerboarding. We discretized the lab-scale fluidized domain into several regions with alternating concentration markings between 0 (blue) and 1 (red). To enhance detectability and traceability, we coarsened the grid to 3x3 cells and marked the concentrations accordingly, as depicted in Figure 5.4a.

5.3 Results

We utilized data-driven recurrence CFD simulations in our investigation of secondary gas distribution and overall solid mixing index patterns in lab-scale fluidized bed simulations. Subsequently, we employ numerical calibration to refine parameters to enhance the quality of our results. We tried to study the distribution of secondary gas injection and the global solid mixing index and the preliminary results are available in Work Package 3 - Application examples. We managed to produce similar results with a speed-up of 3 orders of magnitude (which is capable of matching up to real-time). We understood data-based rCFD needs case-specific calibration to reproduce comparable results with classical two-fluid model simulations. We proposed two different strategies to numerical calibrate the primary gas injection, secondary gas injection, and global solid mixing; 1D calibration by varying face-swap diffusivity value 5.2.2 and 3D calibration by checkerboarding 5.3.2.

5.3.1 Calibration of secondary gas injection

Initially, our approach involved adjusting the value of face swap diffusivity to explore and visualize the changes in secondary gas mass and solid mixing across the domain. We conducted experiments with different face swap values, including 1/8, 1/4, 1/2, 1, 1.12, 1.25, and 1.50, to assess their impact on the distribution and mixing of secondary gas within the simulated system. This systematic variation allowed us to observe how altering the face swap diffusivity affects the behavior and interaction of gas and solid phases, providing valuable insights into the underlying processes governing fluidized bed dynamics.

In scenarios of low concentrations, the quantity of gas molecules is constrained, emphasizing the importance of the diffusion mechanism in distributing gas within a defined volume. Gas molecules migrate from regions of high concentration towards those of lower concentration to attain a uniform distribution.

To gain deeper insights into the global diffusion equilibrium across the domain, we generated a plot illustrating the probability density function of secondary gas concentration. This involved partitioning the domain into 100 discrete bins and analyzing the distribution of gas concentration within each bin. By visualizing the probability density function (PDF), we aimed to examine the overall pattern and variation in secondary gas concentration throughout the simulated system, shedding light on the dynamics of diffusion processes at a macroscopic level. The vertical partitions in Figure 5.2 represent the Probability Density Function (PDF) for varying face swap diffusivity values of gas concentration for the vertical partitioned domain. It's noteworthy that the results obtained from the rCFD simulations with different face swap diffusivity values closely align with those from classical TFM simulations. This observation indicates a consistency between the outcomes of the rCFD approach and the traditional TFM simulations, affirming the validity and reliability of the rCFD method in capturing the behavior of gas concentration under different diffusion conditions. When considering a domain partitioned horizontally, the distribution of secondary gas concentration reveals a uniform spread of gas across the partitions. To replicate this even spread and match the outcomes of classical TFM simulations, higher face swap values were required in the rCFD simulations. This suggests that under horizontal partitioning, the diffusion process necessitates greater face swap diffusivity to achieve results consistent with traditional TFM simulations. The graph depicted in Figure 5.3 illustrates the distribution of calibrated outcomes regarding secondary gas concentration and solid mixing index within the laboratory-scale fluidized bed realm. Initially, the solid particles exhibit a tendency to mix within the initial moments of the numerical simulation, a behavior that aligns closely with the results obtained from comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations. Regarding the secondary gas concentration, our approach involves fine-tuning the parameters of rCFD simulations to achieve a stable fluctuating curve, thereby enhancing the accuracy and reliability of our findings.

5.3.2 Calibration by checkerboarding

We aimed to further explore the alignment between TFM simulations and rCFD simulations, specifically focusing on the local diffusion coefficient. This involved analyzing the diffusive flux across various regions of gas concentration in both simulation approaches. After implementing a checkerboarding pattern in a lab-scale fluidized bed, we conducted classical TFM simulations (full CFD simulations) to visualize how the concentration pattern disperses within the gas phase. The checkerboard pattern diffused into the gas phase, forming a greenish-colored region indicative of regions with diffusion $D_{gas} > 0.5$, while other regions remained unaffected (displaying blue and red colors) as shown in figure 5.4b. The evolution of primary gas became readily apparent through the visualization of the highly diffused region, showcasing the flow dynamics within the system. The rCFD simulations demonstrated excellent agreement with classical TFM (full CFD)

FIGURE 5.2: Probability density function (PDF) of the vertically partitioned domain, with face swap diffusivity values of 1/4, 1/2, and 1.12.

simulations, particularly when addressing local diffusion phenomena. This alignment indicates that the rCFD approach accurately captures the behavior of the system, providing reliable results consistent with traditional simulation methods. However, certain regions exhibit rapid diffusion of flux 5.4c, facilitating the quick dispersion of the checkerboard pattern throughout the domain. Consequently, these regions do not display the characteristic blue and red areas indicative of undiffused regions during the evolution of primary gas. The Probability Density Function (PDF) plot 5.5 offer insights into the distribution of gas concentration within the simulated domain for both classical TFM and rCFD simulations. The peaks observed at concentration levels of 0 and 1 suggest that initially, after initialization, the checkerboard pattern remains relatively localized and does not diffuse extensively. This phenomenon is consistent across both full CFD and rCFD simulations.

However, as the simulation progresses, we observe a stable region of diffused concentration between 0.1 and 0.9. This indicates that the diffusion process becomes more pronounced over time, leading to a more uniform distribution of gas concentration within the domain. The presence of this stable diffused region highlights the significant role of diffusion in shaping the concentration profile and dynamics within the simulated system. Also, the full CFD simulation results show a high peak at concentration 0, which will be calibrated in the next step. Furthermore, in the full

FIGURE 5.3: Plots of secondary gas mass fluctuation and global solid mixing index.

CFD simulation results, there is a notable peak observed at concentration level 0. This peak signifies an area where the concentration remains particularly low. In the subsequent steps, we will calibrate this aspect to better align with the expected behavior and refine the simulation outcomes. This calibration process will involve adjusting parameters or model settings to ensure that the simulation accurately reflects the real-world conditions and behavior of the system.

FIGURE 5.4: Ansys Fluent domain partitions: (a) Checkerboarding application to lab-scale fluidized bed with 3x3 cell orientation; Snapshots of (b) full CFD reference simulation of dissolution of checkerboard concentration region with evolution of primary gas; (c) rCFD simulation of dissolution of checkerboard pattern with diffusive flux dispersion.

FIGURE 5.5: Probability density function (PDF) for classical TFM simulations and data-based rCFD simulations of primary gas concentration.

5.4 Conclusion

This section has presented an overview and methodology of the application of the data-based rCFD method to the lab-scale fluidized bed to simulate particulate processes with a less expensive, and computationally stable approach. We initially applied data-based rCFD to a lab-scale fluidized bed to study secondary gas injection and global solid mixing. We achieved good agreement towards the traditional Two-Fluid Model simulations with a speed-up of more than two orders of magnitude (10,000 times faster), capable of matching up to real-time. In order to numerically calibrate the data-driven rCFD technique, we have addressed both global and local diffusion. This required addressing diffusive flux for 3-dimensional calibration and modifying face swap diffusivity parameters for 1-dimensional calibration. It is extremely difficult to address local diffusion in fluidized bed simulations due to the dynamic nature of fluidized beds, where particles move constantly and behave in different ways.

5.5 Best Practise Guidelines

Utilizing data-driven recurrence computational fluid dynamics (rCFD) is indeed an efficient means to time-extrapolate CFD-DEM/TFM simulations of fluidized beds. Since the data-based rCFD technique is still in its infancy, there aren't many research articles that explain its fundamental ideas in detail. This indicates that there aren't many research works that have been published that go in-depth with the ideas and methods related to this strategy. As such, it can take more time and need the use of fewer resources to fully understand its complexities. When seeking to apply data-driven computational fluid dynamics (CFD) to reactors, whether at laboratory or industrial scales, it is imperative to take into account the following key considerations;

- First and foremost, only pseudo-periodic processes, which are characterized by recurrent flow features, can be used with this time-extrapolation technique as stated in the literature ([2], [5]). Once the flow reaches minimum fluidization velocity, the solid particles exhibit a behavior known as a pseudo-periodic state, where particles move in a manner that appears to be periodic or cyclic.
- In data-driven (transport-based) rCFD, we do not directly tackle transport equations for either the gas or solid phase. Instead, we transfer information within cells. Nonetheless, this method may result in data loss or insufficient data, potentially affecting the precision and trustworthiness of the simulations. Therefore, users should familiarize themselves with fundamental concepts regarding data generation and utilization.
- For the data-driven rCFD method to work, numerical calibration is essential because using standard simulation results alone could result in differences from more conventional

simulation techniques. Initially, we obtained good findings for the global solid mixing of two solid species in the context of modeling a lab-scale fluidized bed to examine solid mixing indices and secondary gas injection. However, we found that to have a good enough agreement with classical TFM simulations, numerical calibration is essential for secondary gas injection. Consequently, to account for variations in diffusive flux within the domain, we developed 3D calibration using a checkerboard pattern and 1D calibration by modifying face swaps.

- It's considered best practice to generate a new database from the beginning whenever there's a requirement to alter the boundaries or operating conditions of the model.
- Even if the user's primary research focus revolves around transport-based rCFD [5], it's highly advisable to begin by familiarizing oneself with the concepts of flow-based rCFD [2]. While the applicability of these two methods may vary, the fundamental concept of recurrence CFD remains consistent across both approaches. Therefore, gaining a solid understanding of flow-based rCFD can provide valuable insights and a strong foundation for delving into transport-based rCFD, despite potential differences in their practical application.

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